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Embracing EU corporate social
responsibility: challenges and
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transformation in Ukraine

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CORPORATE
SOCIAL
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*DIDACTIC RESOURCES FOR THE COURSE
“CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY & RESPONSIBLE
BUSINESS CONDUCT”*

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Certified Training Course

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY / RESPONSIBLE BUSINESS CONDUCT AND SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP **2025**

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Topic 2. Concept and Evolution
of Corporate Social
Responsibility: A Global
Retrospective

Oleh PASKO

<https://eecore.snau.edu.ua/komanda-proiektu/oleg-pasko/>

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Topic 2. Concept and Evolution of Corporate Social Responsibility: A Global Retrospective

1. 1950s–1960s/1970s: CSR and Management
2. 1980s: Operationalization of CSR
3. 1990s: Globalization and CSR
4. 2000s: Strategic Approach to CSR
5. 2010s: CSR and Creation of Shared Value

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1. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

'The term [CSR] is a brilliant one; it means something, but not always the same thing, to everybody'
Votaw, 1973, p. 11

CSR has meant different things at different times, but at its core it refers to “business self-regulation aimed at being socially responsible.”

CSR is the way in which business consistently creates shared value in society through economic development, good governance, stakeholder responsiveness and environmental improvement. Put another way, CSR is an integrated, systemic approach by business that builds, rather than erodes or destroys, economic, social, human and natural capital.

Visser, W. V. (2011). *The Ages and Stages of CSR: Towards the Future with CSR 2.0*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

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1. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1950s-1960s

It was only in the early 1950s that the literature first addressed the concept of a concrete definition of these responsibilities, marking the beginning of the modern definitional framework of corporate social responsibility. In fact, during the 1950s and 1960s, academic research and CSR think tanks focused on the social level of analysis (Lee 2008), giving it practical implications.

While responsible companies had existed for more than a century, the term “corporate social responsibility” was formally introduced in 1953 by American economist Howard Bowen in his publication *Social Responsibilities of the Businessman*. Bowen is therefore often referred to as the father of CSR. First published in 1953, Howard R. Bowen’s book *Social Responsibilities of the Businessman* was the first comprehensive discussion of business ethics and social responsibility. It provided a framework for business leaders and scholars to consider these topics as part of strategic planning and decision-making. Although written in a different era, it continues to be cited frequently for its relevance to modern ethical issues in business operations. Many experts regard it as the foundational book on corporate social responsibility.

Bowen, H. R. (1953). *Social responsibilities of the businessman*. University of Iowa Press.

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1. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1950s-1960s

Bowen believed that large corporations of the time held significant power and that their actions had a substantial impact on society. Therefore, he argued for a change in their decision-making processes to include consideration of their societal impact. As a result of this belief, Bowen (1953) proposed defining a specific set of principles for corporations to fulfill their social responsibilities. In his view, the decisions and actions of business leaders affect stakeholders, employees, and customers, directly influencing the overall quality of life in society (Bowen 1953). With this in mind, Bowen defined the social responsibility of business executives as “the obligations of businessmen to pursue those policies, to make those decisions, or to follow those lines of action which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of our society” (Bowen 1953, p. 6).

Bowen, H. R. (1953). Social responsibilities of the businessman. University of Iowa Press.

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1. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1950s-1960s

A notable figure of this period was Keith Davis (1960), who explained that significant social, economic, and political changes created pressure on business leaders to rethink their role in society and their social responsibilities. Davis (1960) argued that businesspeople have obligations to society in terms of both economic and human values and suggested that, to some extent, social responsibility could be linked to economic returns for the firm (Davis 1960). The significance of Davis's ideas lies in his assertion that "the social responsibilities of businessmen need to be commensurate with their social power" (p. 71) and that avoiding such responsibility would lead to a decline in a firm's social power (Davis 1960).

Davis, K. (1960). Can Business Afford to Ignore Social Responsibilities? *California Management Review*, 2(3), 70–76. <https://doi.org/10.2307/41166246>

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2. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1970s

Archie B. Carroll's 1979 pyramid model remains a key framework for understanding the elements of corporate social responsibility (see figure). These four categories are not mutually exclusive, nor are they intended to represent a continuum from economic issues on one end to social issues on the other. They are neither cumulative nor additive. Rather, they are arranged in the diagram to suggest what may be considered their fundamental role in the evolution of importance. Although all these types of responsibility have always existed simultaneously for business organizations, business history shows an early emphasis on economic, followed by legal aspects, and later on ethical and discretionary considerations. Moreover, any given business responsibility or action can embody economic, legal, ethical, or discretionary motives. The four categories simply remind us that motives or actions can be classified primarily as one or another of these types.

Carroll, A. B. (1979). A Three-Dimensional Conceptual Model of Corporate Performance. The Academy of Management Review, 4(4), 497. <https://doi.org/10.2307/257850>

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2. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1970s

Economic Responsibility. First and foremost, most aspects of corporate social responsibility are economic in nature. A business institution is, above all, the primary economic unit of our society. Therefore, it is responsible for producing the goods and services that society wants and selling them at a profit. All other business roles rest on this fundamental premise.

Legal Responsibility. Just as society has sanctioned the economic system by allowing business to take on the production role as part of the “social contract,” it has also established the basic rules—laws and regulations—under which business is expected to operate. Society expects business to fulfill its economic mission within the framework of legal requirements. The dotted lines in the figure on the slide above indicate that, although we have four types of responsibility, they are to be fulfilled simultaneously, as is the case with economic and legal responsibilities.

Ethical Responsibility. While the first two categories embody ethical norms, there are additional behaviors and activities not codified in law but nonetheless expected by society. Ethical responsibility is poorly defined and, as such, is among the most challenging for business. In recent years, however, ethical responsibility has been strongly emphasized, even as debates over what is ethical continue. Simply put, society expects business to go beyond legal requirements.

Discretionary (Voluntary) Responsibility. Discretionary (or voluntary) responsibilities are those for which society does not clearly communicate expectations—less so than for ethical responsibilities. They are left to individual judgment and choice. Calling these expectations “responsibilities” may be misleading, as they are at the discretion of the business; however, social expectations do exist for business to take on social roles that go beyond those already described. The key point is that if a business does not engage in them, it is not considered unethical per se.

This four-part framework provides categories for the various responsibilities that society expects (or assumes) from business. Each responsibility is only part of the overall social responsibility of business, giving us a more complete definition of what society expects from business:

“The social responsibility of business encompasses the economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations that society has of organizations at a given point in time” (Carroll, 1979, p. 500).

Carroll, A. B. (1979). A Three-Dimensional Conceptual Model of Corporate Performance. The Academy of Management Review, 4(4), 497.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/257850>

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3. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1980s

In 1980, Thomas M. Jones (1980) was perhaps the first author to view CSR as a decision-making process that influences corporate behavior. Jones's (1980) contribution shifted the CSR discussion toward a focus on its operational implementation rather than solely on the concept itself. This led to the development of new structures, models, and methods aimed at assessing CSR from an operational perspective.

Corporate Social Responsibility as a Process

The above discussion brings into sharper focus one basic characteristic of corporate social responsibility, public responsibility, or whatever one chooses to call a voluntary effort on the part of corporate managers to respond to a broader range of social needs. It is very difficult to reach any consensus as to what constitutes socially responsible behavior. To make the point even more strongly, it is virtually impossible to define social responsibility in terms of specific decisions. Very few can be judged absolutely socially responsible and not many can be condemned as socially irresponsible. This leads to the conclusion that corporate social responsibility ought not be seen as a set of outcomes, but as a process.

Corporate behavior should not, in most cases, be judged by the decisions actually reached, but by the process by which they are reached. Broadly stated, corporations need to analyze the social consequences of their decisions before they make them and take steps to minimize the social costs of these decisions when appropriate. The appropriate demand to be made of those who govern large corporations is that they incorporate into their decision-making process means by which broader social concerns are given full consideration. This is corporate social responsibility as a means, not as a set of ends.

Ample precedent exists for this new concept. The philosophical foundations of our political, legal, and judicial systems are based on the notion of fair process. The basic rights held by citizens in this country are virtually always ex-

can be denied, but only through due process of law.

The analogy to the political process is not at all farfetched considering the impact of routine economic decisions of large corporations. When General Motors, General Electric, or General Telephone closes a production facility, changes vendors, or embarks on a minority hiring program, thousands of people may be affected. Political scientist Robert A. Dahl has concluded that this power is indeed political and that corporations should be labeled political systems.¹³ In terms of the social aspects of their decisions, can we honestly expect more of private governments than of public governments? Perhaps the criterion of fair process should apply to both equally.

Implementing Corporate Social Responsibility

Once this concept of corporate social responsibility is accepted, the problem, as before, becomes one of implementation. The new concept leads to an altered set of criteria for evaluating corporate social performance. Emphasis is shifted to the inputs of the decision-making process. Corporate managers would be expected, by whatever means, to fully examine the potential social impact of their decisions before the fact.

The means by which this might be done are varied. Some firms might choose to institute social policy study groups within the existing corporate structure. Some might wish to hire outside consultants. Others might feel that the decision-making process should be formally altered through the addition of special purpose

4. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR 1990s-

Donna J. Wood (1991), seeing the need for a systematic integration of conceptual aspects into a single theory, built on the models of Carroll (1979) and Wartick & Cochran (1985) to develop the Corporate Social Performance (CSP) Model. Wood (1991) identified three dimensions of CSP:

- Principles of corporate social responsibility, including legitimacy (institutional level),
- public responsibility (organizational level), and
- managerial discretion (individual level).

Processes of corporate social responsiveness, including environmental assessment, stakeholder management, and issue management.

Outcomes of corporate behavior, including social impacts, social programs, and social policies.

(Wood, 1991, p. 695)

TABLE 1
The Corporate Social Performance Model

Principles of corporate social responsibility
Institutional principle: legitimacy
Organizational principle: public responsibility
Individual principle: managerial discretion
Processes of corporate social responsiveness
Environmental assessment
Stakeholder management
Issues management
Outcomes of corporate behavior
Social impacts
Social programs
Social policies

4. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1990s

Also in 1991, Carroll (1991) introduced the “**Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility**” to provide a practical approach to CSR for managers who needed to balance their obligations to shareholders with emerging responsibilities toward a broader range of stakeholders, stemming from new U.S. government bodies and regulations.

In the **CSR Pyramid**, Carroll (1991) outlined what he considered the four essential duties of any company:

- **Economic responsibilities**, forming the foundation for the other levels of the pyramid.
- **Legal responsibilities** of the firm.
- **Ethical responsibilities**, guiding corporate conduct beyond legal compliance.
- **Philanthropic responsibilities**, referring to the corporation’s contribution to improving the quality of life in society.

In addition to visually presenting CSR in terms of these responsibilities, Carroll (1991) argued that a company should be a good corporate citizen—a concept he further developed in the late 1990s.

(Carroll, 1991, p. 42)

Figure 3
The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility

Carroll, A. B. (1991). The pyramid of corporate social responsibility: Toward the moral management of organizational stakeholders. *Business Horizons*, 34(4), 39–48. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0007-6813\(91\)90005-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0007-6813(91)90005-G)

1990s

4. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

(Carroll, 1991, p. 40)

Figure 1
Economic and Legal Components of Corporate Social Responsibility

Economic Components (Responsibilities)	Legal Components (Responsibilities)
1. It is important to perform in a manner consistent with maximizing earnings per share.	1. It is important to perform in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.
2. It is important to be committed to being as profitable as possible.	2. It is important to comply with various federal, state, and local regulations.
3. It is important to maintain a strong competitive position.	3. It is important to be a law-abiding corporate citizen.
4. It is important to maintain a high level of operating efficiency.	4. It is important that a successful firm be defined as one that fulfills its legal obligations.
5. It is important that a successful firm be defined as one that is consistently profitable.	5. It is important to provide goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.

(Carroll, 1991, p. 40)

Figure 2
Ethical and Philanthropic Components of Corporate Social Responsibility

Ethical Components (Responsibilities)	Philanthropic Components (Responsibilities)
1. It is important to perform in a manner consistent with expectations of societal mores and ethical norms.	1. It is important to perform in a manner consistent with the philanthropic and charitable expectations of society.
2. It is important to recognize and respect new or evolving ethical/moral norms adopted by society.	2. It is important to assist the fine and performing arts.
3. It is important to prevent ethical norms from being compromised in order to achieve corporate goals.	3. It is important that managers and employees participate in voluntary and charitable activities within their local communities.
4. It is important that good corporate citizenship be defined as doing what is expected morally or ethically.	4. It is important to provide assistance to private and public educational institutions.
5. It is important to recognize that corporate integrity and ethical behavior go beyond mere compliance with laws and regulations.	5. It is important to assist voluntarily those projects that enhance a community's "quality of life."

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4. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR 1990s

(Burke & Logsdon, 1996, p. 500)

A notable contribution in the 1990s to the CSR concept was made by **Burke and Logsdon (1996)**, who aimed to find evidence of a link between CSR and positive financial outcomes for firms. They were likely among the first to evaluate the benefits of **strategic CSR implementation**.

For Burke and Logsdon, CSR could be applied with a strategic approach to support a company's core business activities and, as a result, improve its effectiveness in achieving its primary objectives.

Burke, L., & Logsdon, J. M. (1996). How corporate social responsibility pays off. *Long Range Planning*, 29(4), 495–502.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-6301\(96\)00041-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-6301(96)00041-6)

		STRATEGIC DIMENSION					STRATEGIC OUTCOME
		Centrality	Specificity	Proactivity	Voluntarism	Visibility	Value created
CSR BEHAVIOUR	Philanthropic contributions (S, product, time)	Computer donations to schools by computer mfrs. Engineering research fellowships	Accustom new users to firm's products vs competitors'		Community support		Customer loyalty Future purchasers
	Employee benefits (direct or indirect)		Health/wellness Day care Flex-time	New or uncommon benefits Higher employee loyalty	Employee loyalty and morale	Internal: employee loyalty and morale	Productivity gains
	Environment management (health, safety, pollution)	New products e.g. 'green' Process innovation esp. re pollution	Patent or innovation edge in product or process development	Learning curve advantages	Positive relations with regulators	Public relations and/or marketing advantage	New products or markets
	Political activity (PAC, lobby or information, independent or industry)	Favourable change in economic or social regulations	New business opportunities if pre-positioned to take advantage of new rules	Pre-positioning for changes in regulations			New product or geographic market opportunities
	Product or service related characteristics, innovations or processes	Product reformulations e.g. 'green' improved design, e.g. fuel efficiency new products, e.g. airbags	Patent or innovation edge first-to-market brand loyalty	Environmental scanning to create edge in design or product ideas		First-to-market or leadership benefits	New product on new markets Edge in meeting emergency needs

4. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1990s

(Burke & Logsdon, 1996)

Additionally, Burke and Logsdon (1996) identified **five dimensions of strategic CSR** that they considered essential for achieving business objectives and creating value:

- 1. Centrality** – the extent to which CSR is close to or aligned with the company’s mission and goals.
- 2. Specificity** – the ability to generate specific, tangible benefits for the firm.
- 3. Proactivity** – the ability to develop policies that anticipate and respond to social trends.
- 4. Voluntarism** – the discretionary decision-making process free from external compliance requirements.
- 5. Visibility** – the degree to which CSR is observable and recognized by internal and external stakeholders.

They argued that implementing strategic CSR through these five dimensions leads to **value creation** that can be identified and measured, though it remains bounded by the firm’s economic benefit.

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4. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1990s

Another key contribution to the CSR debate came from the concept of the “Triple Bottom Line”, first developed by Elkington in 1994 as a foundation for sustainable development, balancing the social, environmental, and economic impacts of a company. Later, Elkington (1997) explained that achieving outstanding results in these three areas requires effective and long-term partnerships between the private and public sectors, as well as among stakeholders. By the late 1990s, the Triple Bottom Line had become a popular practical approach to sustainability, remaining relevant in CSR discussions as it emphasizes that corporations should pursue socially and environmentally responsible behavior while aligning it with their economic goals.

Elkington, J. (1997). *Cannibals with Forks: The triple bottom line of 21st century business*. Capstone: Oxford.

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5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

2000s

In the early 21st century, Craig Smith (2001) explained that corporate policy had shifted in response to societal interests, often resulting in a positive social impact.

This meant that the scope of corporate social responsibility (from a business perspective) now covered a wider range of stakeholders.

He proposed a new definition:

“Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) refers to a firm’s obligations to its stakeholders — the people affected by corporate policies and practices. These obligations go beyond the firm’s legal requirements and duties to its shareholders. Fulfilling them is aimed at minimizing any harm and maximizing the firm’s long-term beneficial impact on society” (Smith, 2001, p. 142).

Smith, N. C. (2001). Changes in corporate practices in response to public interest advocacy and actions. In P. N. B. a. G. T. Gundlach (Ed.), Handbook of Marketing and Society. Thousand Oaks.

5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

2000s

Marrewijk (2003) presented an overview of CSR and corporate sustainability concepts, recognizing this new perspective on CSR. He described this societal approach to CSR as a strategic response to emerging corporate challenges, which he explained as the result of evolving roles and responsibilities of each sector of society. For Marrewijk (2003), firms address these challenges by adopting varying levels of CSR integration into their corporate structure - a topic still debated in the literature.

Accordingly, Marrewijk (2003) proposed five interpretations of his corporate sustainable development concept, which he considered the modern understanding of CSR. These interpretations can be understood as levels of CSR integration into company policy and structure.

The **holistic interpretation** of Marrewijk (2003) is perhaps the most relevant for the purpose of our lecture, as it represents **full CSR integration** - driven by the pursuit of sustainable development in the understanding that companies now play a new role in society and, consequently, must make strategic decisions to adapt to their social context.

Marrewijk, 2003, p. 100

1. legislation and maintenance (control)
2. competition and cooperation (market)
3. collective action and participation

Figure 1. State, business and civil society.

2000s

5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

1. *Compliance-driven CS* (Blue): CS at this level consists of providing welfare to society, within the limits of regulations from the rightful authorities. In addition, organizations might respond to charity and stewardship considerations. The motivation for CS is that CS is perceived as a duty and obligation, or correct behaviour.
2. *Profit-driven CS* (Orange): CS at this level consists of the integration of social, ethical and ecological aspects into business operations and decision-making, provided it contributes to the financial bottom line. The motivation for CS is a business case: CS is promoted if profitable, for example because of an improved reputation in various markets (customers/employees/shareholders).
3. *Caring CS* (Green): CS consists of balancing economic, social and ecological concerns, which are all three important in themselves. CS initiatives go beyond legal compliance and beyond profit considerations. The motivation for CS is that human potential, social responsibility and care for the planet are as such important.
4. *Synergistic CS* (Yellow): CS consists of a search for well-balanced, functional solutions creating value in the economic, social and ecological realms of corporate performance, in a synergistic, win-together approach with all relevant stakeholders. The motivation for CS is that sustainability is important in itself, especially because it is recognised as being the inevitable direction progress takes.
5. *Holistic CS* (Turquoise): CS is fully integrated and embedded in every aspect of the organization, aimed at contributing to the quality and continuation of life of every being and entity, now and in the future. The motivation for CS is that sustainability is the only alternative since all beings and phenomena are mutually interdependent. Each person or organization therefore has a universal responsibility towards all other beings.

read CS as CS/CSR

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5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

2000s

Werther and Chandler (2005) further explored the **strategic response** companies make to their social context.

In their first co-authored work, they focused on implementing **strategic CSR** as part of brand management, aiming to achieve and maintain legitimacy in a global context.

The relevance of their work lies in the emphasis on shifting CSR from being a "*minimal obligation... to a strategic necessity*" (Werther & Chandler, 2005, p. 319).

They argued that effective SCSR integration must come from "*a genuine commitment to change and self-reflection*" (p. 322) and should follow a **top-down approach** throughout all company operations to become a **sustainable competitive advantage**.

Even though their CSR approach mainly addressed **competitiveness** and **corporate legitimacy**, their main contribution was the **explicit recognition of CSR as a strategic necessity**, making it indispensable for any corporation.

8. Strategic CSR: Good business sense

For brand-based firms, Archie Carroll's (Carroll, 1979) four-stage hierarchy of social responsibility collapses into one of economic viability and social legitimacy. As Bansal and Bogner (2002, p. 277) reason:

“An organization’s image is the cumulative assessments of the firm by its stakeholders over time. If the firm conforms to stakeholder expectations, it builds legitimacy. ... this helps build stronger relationships and trust with its stakeholders, and ... can assist the organization in the face of adverse ... conditions.”

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5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

2000s

Porter and Kramer's (2011) landmark article "**Creating Shared Value**" (CSV) marked a major breakthrough in linking profit generation with solving societal problems - the idea of "*doing well by doing good.*"

Creating Shared Value (CSV) refers to a **strategic process** through which corporations can turn social issues into business opportunities (Menghwar & Daood, 2021, p. 466).

The strategic CSV approach to addressing societal challenges - and its close connection to **strategic corporate social responsibility** and **stakeholder theory** - keeps the concept central in both corporate and

Porter, M.E., Kramer, M.R. (2006) Strategy & society: The link between competitive advantage and corporate social responsibility, Harvard Business Review, 84 (12), pp. 78-92 <https://hbr.org/2006/12/strategy-and-society-the-link-between-competitive-advantage-and-corporate-social-responsibility>

Menghwar, P. S., & Daood, A. (2021). Creating shared value: A systematic review, synthesis and integrative perspective. International Journal of Management Reviews, 23(4), 466–485. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijmr.12252>

2000s

5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

Porter and Kramer (2006) argue that companies can achieve a competitive advantage through CSR by strategically addressing their competitive context in a way that creates shared value delivering benefits to society while simultaneously improving the firm’s competitiveness. According to Porter and Kramer (2006), a company should: Look internally to map the social impact of its value chain, identifying both the positive and negative effects of its operations on society. Focus on the areas with the greatest strategic value for improvement. Look externally to understand how the social context affects its performance and outcomes.

Differences between CSR i CSV <https://bit.ly/3lhyQop>

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY CSR	CREATING SHARED VALUE CSV
Addressing societal needs and challenges by giving back + doing no/less harm	Addressing societal needs and challenges with a business model
Doing good	Doing well by doing good
Discretionary or in response to external pressures, no relation with competitiveness	Integral to competing: propels competitive advantage in new, unlocked markets
Separate from profit maximizing, philanthropy	Integral to profit maximizing
Agenda determined by external factors and often personal or departments’ preference	Agenda company, sector and market specific
No real influence on innovation, other than incremental	Initiates radical innovation and incremental innovation at scale
Operational and tactical issue	Strategical priority, at the heart of business
Scalable, but from cost perspective	Scalable, with profit increasing
Seen as costs and legitimization of operations for investors	Seen as commercial opportunities for investors

Porter, M.E., Kramer, M.R. (2006) *Strategy & society: The link between competitive advantage and corporate social responsibility*, Harvard Business Review, 84 (12), pp. 78-92 <https://hbr.org/2006/12/strategy-and-society-the-link-between-competitive-advantage-and-corporate-social-responsibility>

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5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

2000s

Mark Kramer : <https://bit.ly/39ywZco>

This passage explains the distinction between Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Creating Shared Value (CSV) as outlined by Michael Porter and his co-author:

CSR is generally perceived as a cost center - activities done out of responsibility, often seen as expenses necessary for doing business (e.g., sustainability reporting). CSV is about value creation - finding new business opportunities that generate profit, open new markets, and improve competitive positioning while addressing social issues (e.g., developing a new product like the Chevy Volt).

While the two concepts can overlap (“doing well by doing good”), CSV focuses on integrating social problem-solving directly into the core business strategy to create both economic and societal value. CSR, in contrast, is often more about fulfilling obligations rather than generating competitive advantage.

They also note that leading companies’ approach to social impact has evolved significantly in the last decade, whether called “new CSR” or “shared value.”

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5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

2000s

Porter and Kramer (2006) provided a new understanding of corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a means of maximising the interdependence between business and society through a holistic approach to corporate activities. They proposed that CSR should serve as a comprehensive business framework rather than a limited, goal-oriented tool. In fact, Porter and Kramer (2006) argued that when CSR is applied without a holistic approach and focuses solely on specific objectives - such as obtaining a social licence to operate, maintaining or enhancing reputational status, or satisfying stakeholder demands - it restricts the company's potential to create social benefits while simultaneously supporting its business objectives.

Porter, M.E., Kramer, M.R. (2006) Strategy & society: The link between competitive advantage and corporate social responsibility, Harvard Business Review, 84 (12), pp. 78-92 <https://hbr.org/2006/12/strategy-and-society-the-link-between-competitive-advantage-and-corporate-social-responsibility>

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5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

2000s

The concept of value creation through CSR was supported by Husted and Allen (2007), who conducted a survey of the largest companies in Spain by number of employees to identify the key strategic aspects these companies consider important for creating value through CSR. To this end, Husted and Allen (2007) drew on four of the five dimensions of strategic CSR established by Burke and Logsdon (1996), and subsequently provided their own definition of CSR as a company's ability to: "(1) ensure an aligned focus on the firm's portfolio of resources and assets (centrality); (2) anticipate competitors in acquiring strategic factors (proactivity); (3) create reputational advantage through stakeholders' awareness of the firm's behaviour (visibility); and (4) ensure that the created added value accrues to the firm (appropriability)" (Husted & Allen, 2007, p. 596). It is noteworthy that Husted and Allen (2007) did not include the voluntarism dimension proposed by Burke and Logsdon (1996) in their definition of strategic CSR, although they acknowledged its relevance as a key dimension of CSR for value creation.

The Burke and Logsdon framework provides a useful starting point for this work. The framework was proposed as a practical instrument for helping managers develop CSR strategies that "pay off"; it was not a fully developed model with testable hypotheses. Accordingly, we have translated the framework into the resource-based view, and defined strategic CSR as the firm's ability to: 1) provide a coherent focus to a portfolio of firm resources and assets (centrality); 2) anticipate competitors in acquiring strategic factors (proactivity); 3) build reputation advantage through customer knowledge of firm behavior (visibility); 4) ensure that the added value created goes to the firm (appropriability).⁷ Voluntarism, we should note, is missing from this description of strategic CSR, though it is a key variable in CSR value creation. We will return to this issue below in the theory section of the paper.

Husted, B. W., & Allen, D. B. (2007). Strategic Corporate Social Responsibility and Value Creation among Large Firms. *Long Range Planning*, 40(6), 594–610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2007.07.001>

5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR 2000s

Moreover, the most relevant contributions of Husted and Allen (2007) to the concept of CSR are twofold: first, CSR generates new areas of opportunity through a constant pursuit of value creation, which in turn leads to innovation. Second, the implementation of CSR aimed at creating value is inevitably linked to social requirements.

(Husted & Allen, 2007, p. 598)

Table 1. A Comparison of Traditional CSR, Strategic CSR, and Traditional Strategy

Strategic Dimensions	Different Approaches to CSR and Strategy		
	Traditional CSR	Traditional Strategy	Strategic CSR
Visibility	Irrelevant: Doing good is its own reward – and is profitable in the long run.	Build customer awareness of product and brand.	Building customer and stakeholder awareness of product with CSR value added.
Appropriability	Irrelevant: Doing good is its own reward – and profitable in the long run.	Manage supplier, customer, and competitor relations to capture value added for firm.	Manage stakeholder relations to capture value added for the firm.
Voluntarism	Participate in social action beyond that demanded by the firm’s interests and the law.	Firm innovation based on ability to learn: non – deterministic behavior.	Participate in social action beyond that demanded by law.
Centrality	Irrelevant: Doing good is tied to social need and not to core business mission.	Create value via product/ service innovation.	Create value via product/ service innovation linked to social issues.
Proactivity	Anticipate changes in social issues.	First-mover advantage.	Anticipate changes in social issues that present market opportunities.

Husted, B. W., & Allen, D. B. (2007). Strategic Corporate Social Responsibility and Value Creation among Large Firms. *Long Range Planning*, 40(6), 594–610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2007.07.001>

5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR 2000s

(HESLIN & OCHOA, 2008, p. 130)

The belief in achieving competitive advantage and creating value through CSR was further developed by Heslin and Ochoa (2008), who argued that even when CSR practices are most effective when specifically designed, they still follow general principles. To support their hypothesis, Heslin and Ochoa (2008) analyzed 21 exemplary CSR practices and observed that seven general principles guide the strategic approach to CSR in the selected companies: cultivate essential talents, develop new markets, protect employee well-being, reduce environmental impact, profit from by-products, engage customers, and green the supply chain.

TABLE 2 STRATEGIC CSR PRINCIPLES AND EXEMPLARY PRACTICES

STRATEGIC CSR PRINCIPLES	CORPORATION	EXEMPLARY STRATEGIC CSR PRACTICES
1. Cultivate needed talent	<i>Marriott</i> <i>Microsoft</i> <i>GlaxoSmithKline</i>	Provide extraordinary career opportunities Nurture required IT talent Expand access to medications
2. Develop new markets	<i>Philips Electronics</i> <i>Globe Telecom</i> <i>Whole Foods</i>	Produce resource-efficient products Create first-time consumers Specialize in organic products
3. Protect labor welfare	<i>Levi Strauss</i> <i>Odegard & Rugmark</i> <i>Starbucks</i>	Replace exploitation with education Certify ethical production Enhance farmers' productivity and welfare
4. Reduce your environmental footprint	<i>DuPont</i> <i>Ethel M</i> <i>Norsk Hydro</i>	Create more value and less "stuff" Produce abundant life from wastewater Renew raw materials
5. Profit from by-products	<i>Fuji Xerox</i> <i>Shaw Industries</i> <i>Manildra</i>	Redesign products for learning and profits Adopt cradle-to-cradle manufacturing Convert grain and starch waste to fuels and food
6. Involve customers	<i>Target</i> <i>Hewlett-Packard</i> <i>Patagonia</i>	Enable customers to improve education Reduce the environmental cost of IT use Educate and engage customers
7. Green your supply chain	<i>Nestle</i> <i>Wal-Mart</i> <i>S.C. Johnson</i>	Optimize transportation Reduce packaging across the supply chain Identify, publicize and reward greener alternatives

HESLIN, P. A., & OCHOA, J. D. (2008). Understanding and developing strategic corporate social responsibility. *Organizational Dynamics*, 37(2), 125–144.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2008.02.002>

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2000s

5. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

The exemplary CSR practices presented by Heslin and Ochoa (2008) provide insight into the potential benefits of CSR for creating shared value for companies themselves, their stakeholders, and the social context in which firms operate. Based on the work of Heslin and Ochoa (2008), it appears that, at least for some globally renowned companies, the belief in creating shared value has become a driving force for integrating global and complex issues into corporate CSR policies. By the late 2000s, it had become clear that CSR holds the potential to generate shared value and address social challenges.

(HESLIN & OCHOA, 2008, p. 130)

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Understanding and developing strategic corporate social responsibility

PETER A. HESLIN¹

JENNA D. OCHOA

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2010s

6. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

The concept of Creating Shared Value (CSV) was further developed by Porter and Kramer (2011), who described it as a necessary step in the evolution of business and defined it as: “policies and operating practices that enhance the competitiveness of a company while simultaneously advancing the economic and social conditions in the communities in which it operates. Creating shared value focuses on identifying and expanding the connections between societal and economic progress” (Porter & Kramer, 2011, p. 2). For Porter and Kramer (2011), the need for CSV is partly the result of conventional narrow business strategies that often fail to take into account the broader factors influencing long-term success. Notably, Porter and Kramer (2011) categorize CSR within this outdated and limited approach, seeing it as having emerged primarily as a way to improve corporate reputation. Consequently, they argue that CSV should replace CSR.

Porter, M. E., & Kramer, M. R. (2011). Creating shared value. Harvard Business Review(January-February)
https://moodle.luniversitenumérique.fr/pluginfile.php/6274/mod_folder/content/0/8.%20La%20valeur%20partage%CC%81e%20-%20Micheal%20Porter.pdf

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6. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

Perhaps the most relevant contribution of Porter and Kramer (2011) stems from their assertion that “the purpose of the corporation must be redefined as creating shared value” (p. 2) and their indication that the first step in this process is identifying societal needs, as well as the benefits or harm that a business embodies in its products. Accordingly, Porter and Kramer (2011) identified three ways of creating shared value:

- 1.Reconceiving products and markets
- 2.Redefining productivity in the value chain
- 3.Enabling the development of supportive industry clusters in the locations where the company operates

Porter, M. E., & Kramer, M. R. (2011). Creating shared value. Harvard Business Review(January-February)
https://moodle.luniversitenumérique.fr/pluginfile.php/6274/mod_folder/content/0/8.%20La%20valeur%20partage%CC%81e%20-%20Micheal%20Porter.pdf

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6. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

Trapp (2012) provided an example of third-generation CSR through a study of Vattenfall, a Swedish state-owned energy company, which in 2008 launched a stakeholder engagement campaign supported by CSR initiatives aimed at mitigating the effects of climate change. The case demonstrated that even though the Vattenfall campaign addressed clear social and global issues (climate change), it still reflected typical business objectives—in this case, generating interest in the company's environmental efforts and creating a brand image associated with combating climate change, which served as a first-step competitive advantage. Thus, Trapp (2012) contributed to the CSR concept by highlighting new roles and responsibilities that corporations are prepared to assume in order to create shared value.

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6. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

In the third edition of *Strategic Corporate Social Responsibility* by Chandler and Werther (2013), the authors reaffirmed the relevance of creating shared value, consistently emphasized in previous editions, and underscored its importance by changing the book's subtitle from *Stakeholders in a Global Environment* to the new version *Stakeholders, Globalization, and Sustainable Value Creation*. In fact, in this third edition, Chandler and Werther (2013) argue that CSR has the potential to create sustainable value, and that the first step in doing so is to identify social issues for which the company can create a market with effective and socially responsible solutions. Later, in the fourth and final edition, Chandler (2016) reflects on the evolution of CSR and its growing recognition as a central element in corporate strategic decision-making, as well as in day-to-day operations. From this edition, it is evident that Chandler (2016) sees sustainable value creation as one of the main goals of CSR. Indeed, the subtitle of the fourth edition, *Creating Sustainable Value*, summarizes Chandler's (2016) new perspective on CSR, according to which "value creation cannot be avoided... [rather] it must be embraced" (p. xxvii).

Chandler, D. (2016). *Strategic corporate social responsibility: sustainable value creation. United States of America: SAGE Publications.*

Chandler, D., & Werther, W. B. (2013). *Strategic corporate social responsibility: stakeholders, globalization, and sustainable value creation* (3rd ed.). United States of America: SAGE Publications.

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2010s

6. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

In 2015, Carroll revisited CSR through a review of the concept's evolution, complementing his literature reviews from 1999 and 2010. This time, however, he examined competing and complementary concepts that have become part of the modern business lexicon. Carroll (2015) considered the notions of stakeholder engagement and management, business ethics, corporate citizenship, corporate sustainability, and creating shared value, concluding that all of them are interconnected and overlapping. In particular, Carroll (2015) noted that these concepts have all been incorporated into CSR, which he defines as both a benchmark and the central component of the socially responsible business movement.

stakeholder engagement and management,
business ethics,
corporate citizenship,
corporate Sustainability,
and the creation of shared value

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6. What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR 2010s

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Carroll, A. B. (2015). Corporate social responsibility. *Organizational Dynamics*, 44(2), 87–96.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2015.02.002>

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What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

Latapí Agudelo, M. A., Jóhannsdóttir, L., & Davídsdóttir, B. (2019). A literature review of the history and evolution of corporate social responsibility. *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40991-018-0039-y>

HISTORY OF CSR

1960
For **Davis**, businessmen have a broad obligation towards society in terms of economic and human values. As a consequence, the "social responsibilities of businessmen need to be commensurate with their social power" (p. 71)

1970'S
The term **Corporate Social Responsibility** became increasingly popular

1979
For **Carroll**, CSR encompasses economic, legal, ethical, and discretionary expectations that society has of organizations at any given point

1991
Wood creates a model of Corporate Social Performance based on the principles of CSR and identifies the outcomes of corporate behavior as social impacts

1996
Burke and Logsdon defined 5 dimensions of **strategic CSR** that result in identifiable and measurable value creation (in the form of economic benefits for the firm)

2003
For **Marrewijk**, SCSR is a response to the new roles and responsibilities of each sector of society

1953
Bowen defined that the social responsibility of business executives is to make decisions according to the values of our society

1970-71
The **Committee for Economic Development (USA)** provided a new understanding to the role of corporations by stating that: "business functions by public consent, and its basic purpose is to serve constructively the needs of society" (p. 11)
"Business exists to serve society" (Committee for Economic Development (USA), 1971, p. 16)

1980
Jones claims that CSR should be seen as a **decision making process** that would influence corporate behavior

1991
Carroll represents the four main responsibilities of companies with the **Pyramid of CSR** and states that companies should be **good corporate citizens**

2001
For **Lantos**, CSR responds to the implicit social contract between business and society and can become **strategic** when it is part of the company's management plans for generating profits

2006
For **Porter and Kramer**, SCSR helps companies achieve a competitive advantage that results in the **creation of shared value**

2008
Heslin and Ochoa explain that even when SCSR should be tailor made it still follows 7 common principles: cultivate the needed talent, develop new markets, protect labor welfare, reduce the environmental footprint, profit from by-products, involve customers, and green the supply chain.

2012
Trapp sees CSR* as the moment in which corporations reflect their concerns about social and global issues on their activities, even when some of those concerns might not be directly linked to their core business

2015
Carroll concluded that the concepts of stakeholder engagement and management, business ethics, corporate citizenship, corporate sustainability, and the creation of shared value are all interrelated and overlapping and all of them have been incorporated into CSR. Carroll defines CSR as the **benchmark** and central piece for the **socially responsible movement**

2005
Chandler and Werther recognized a shift in social responsibility that transformed "CSR from being a minimal commitment...to becoming a strategic necessity" (p. 319) which can translate into a sustainable competitive advantage

2007
For **Husted and Allen**, SCSR generates new areas of opportunity through the constant drive for **creating value**, which is at the same time inevitably linked to social demands

2011
Porter and Kramer claim that "the purpose of the corporation must be redefined as **creating shared value**" (p. 2) and as such the concept of Creating Shared Value (CSV) should replace CSR

2013
Chandler and Werther see SCSR as central to a company's strategic decision making as well as to their day-to-day operations and claim that through it, firms can create market-based products/services in an efficient and socially responsible way

2016
Chandler defines the generation of **sustainable value** as the main objective of SCSR

*Referring for Trapp's third generation of CSR

What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

Latapí Agudelo, M. A., Jóhannsdóttir, L., & Davídsdóttir, B. (2019). A literature review of the history and evolution of corporate social responsibility. *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40991-018-0039-y>

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What is Corporate Social Responsibility? Evolution of CSR

Yang, M., Bento, P., & Akbar, A. (2019). Does CSR Influence Firm Performance Indicators? Evidence from Chinese Pharmaceutical Enterprises. *Sustainability*, 11(20), 5656. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11205656>

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Topic 2. Concept and Evolution of Corporate Social Responsibility: A Global Retrospective

1. 1950s–1960s/1970s: CSR and Management
2. 1980s: Operationalization of CSR
3. 1990s: Globalization and CSR
4. 2000s: Strategic Approach to CSR
5. 2010s: CSR and Creation of Shared Value

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responsibility: challenges and
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CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY / RESPONSIBLE BUSINESS CONDUCT AND SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP **2025**

Topic 3. The Conceptual Evolution
of Corporate Social Responsibility:
The Role of Context and
Institutional Conditions (4 hours)

Oleh PASKO

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The Conceptual Evolution of Corporate Social Responsibility: The Role of Context and Institutional Conditions

1. The Role of Context in the Evolution and Understanding of Corporate Social Responsibility
2. Conceptual Model of the Evolution and Development of Corporate Social Responsibility
3. History
4. Religion and Philosophical Traditions
5. Culture, Social Norms, and Customs
6. Geography
7. Political Structures
8. Level of Economic Development
9. Civil Society Institutions
10. Safety Networks

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1. The Role of Context in the Evolution and Understanding of Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is not an exclusively Western concept. While it may be true that CSR research has been conducted over a long period in Western academic institutions, and that CSR practices are more common among company managers in the West than elsewhere, the concept exists worldwide.

There are also conflicting theories about the emergence of CSR concepts and practices in developing countries: whether these concepts originate from internal sources or are imported from developed Western countries as part of a business conduct model brought by transnational companies as they expanded across the globe.

Visser, Wayne, & Tolhurst, N. (Eds.). (2017). *The World Guide to CSR*. Routledge.

<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351278928>

Idowu, S. O. (Ed.). (2021). *Current Global Practices of Corporate Social Responsibility*. Springer International Publishing.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-68386-3>

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1. The Role of Context in the Evolution and Understanding of Corporate Social Responsibility

The aim here, however, is not to resolve these conflicting theories. Our goal is to have an analytical tool—a framework for studying the nature of Corporate Social Responsibility—regardless of where it is practiced. This is to emphasise the importance of context. This analytical tool includes eight elements and is designed to help us interpret the contextual conditions of a country, culture, and/or region, as well as to understand why and how CSR practices may differ in Ukraine compared to those in China, India, or the countries of the Global North.

Örtenblad, A. (2016). Research Handbook on Corporate Social Responsibility in Context. Edward Elgar Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474806>

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1. The Role of Context in the Evolution and Understanding of Corporate Social Responsibility

To better understand how CSR has evolved and how it is actually practiced in a given country or region, it is essential to examine and comprehend the context in which CSR emerged.

To assist in this process, this session introduces an analytical tool - an organisational framework - that can help systematically study the development of CSR in a specific country and explain why it may differ significantly from the understanding and practices found in Western countries.

Örtenblad, A. (2016). Research Handbook on Corporate Social Responsibility in Context. Edward Elgar Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474806>

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1. The Role of Context in the Evolution and Understanding of Corporate Social Responsibility

The eight elements of this analytical tool are:

1. History
2. Religion (or prevailing philosophical thought)
3. Social norms, customs, and culture
4. Geography
5. Political structures
6. Level of economic development
7. Civil society institutions
8. Prevailing “safety net” provisions

The first four elements are relatively static and serve to describe how corporate social responsibility is understood in a given country. The latter four elements are more dynamic and help explain how the study and practice of CSR evolve over time in that country.

Örtenblad, A. (2016). Research Handbook on Corporate Social Responsibility in Context. Edward Elgar Publishing.

<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474806>

2. Conceptual Model of the Evolution and Development of Corporate Social Responsibility

It should be understood that these elements do not carry equal weight; some are more important than others, and their relative significance will vary from one country, culture, or region to another. Let us examine these elements in more detail to understand how each can influence the perception and practice of CSR.

3. History

China

For literally thousands of years, the country experienced dynastic rule with little or no opportunity to develop a business culture or business mindset. Even when this ended nearly one hundred years ago, the turmoil between nationalists and communists, followed by the communist government, did not allow private property ownership or free market activity. The state controlled the economy. Only after Mao Zedong's death in 1976 and Deng Xiaoping's subsequent opening of the country a year or two later to certain market-based economic decisions did even the concept of the corporation begin to take root. It is therefore not surprising that the practice and study of corporate social responsibility in China are still in their infancy compared to the West.

3. History

India

Despite the fact that the country can still be considered developing, its more than three centuries of control and dominance by Great Britain could not fail to influence the development of its concept of corporate social responsibility.

The very different histories of these two nations help explain why CSR is perceived and practiced differently in each country.

4. Religion

Religion and Philosophical Traditions

Business ethics textbooks consistently tell us that our thinking and understanding of ethical issues-what is right and wrong, good and bad-are shaped by our religious and/or philosophical heritage. It seems reasonable to extend this idea to our understanding of corporate social responsibility. In the West, we are products of our Judeo-Christian heritage. India, in contrast, has been influenced by both Islam and Hinduism at various points in its history and in different regions of the country.

4. Religion

Religion and Philosophical Traditions

China and other East Asian countries have for centuries been influenced by Buddhist and Daoist teachings.

A broad belt of countries stretching from North Africa through the Middle East and into parts of East Asia has been predominantly Muslim for a thousand years or more.

Does it not make sense, then, that corporate social responsibility in each of these regions would carry somewhat different meanings?

4. Religion

Religion and Philosophical Traditions

However, we should be careful not to overemphasize this distinction.

In all three Abrahamic religions - Christianity, Judaism, and Islam-the concept of charity is considered an important virtue. Thus, it can be assumed that enterprises operating in any of these three religious environments would be expected to take on commitments and responsibilities beyond mere profit accumulation, extending to the broader societies in which they operate.

Further scholarly research is needed to assess the extent to which dominant religion and philosophical thought influence the concept of corporate social responsibility.

5. Culture

CULTURE, SOCIAL NORMS, AND HABITS

Countries, regions, and cultures differ in how their citizens relate to one another and in what they consider important.

Americans, for example, take pride in their individualism and are known for it. Each person is expected – and theoretically able - to achieve the most from themselves through hard work, energy, and initiative.

Other societies, particularly in Africa, India, and the East, are more collectivist in their thinking. The welfare of the clan, village, or tribe takes precedence over the welfare of the individual.

China can again serve as an example of a more collectivist society. Throughout Chinese history, during millennia of dynastic rule and under communist governance since the founding of the People’s Republic of China in 1949, individual well-being has been subordinated to the welfare of the village, province, or nation. Ownership and management of property were functions of the government, which presumably acted in the best interests of society as a whole.

5. Culture

CULTURE, SOCIAL NORMS, AND HABITS

Another social norm worth noting is the importance of family. In India, China, and other Eastern countries, it is still common for several generations of the same family to live together. Although the custom is weakening, marriages are still often arranged by the families of the young couple. The bride and groom typically do not establish their own household; instead, the bride leaves her family and moves into the groom’s family, becoming part of it. Ancestor worship remains common in some parts of China.

5. Culture

CULTURE, SOCIAL NORMS, AND HABITS

How different are these social norms in the East compared to the West?

The importance of family and the spectrum of individualism versus collectivism are not merely curiosities for sociologists and anthropologists to study. They help define what corporate social responsibility means and should mean. In a collectivist society-perhaps in Bangladesh-the right of an individual worker to a safe workplace, let alone comfort, and the right to humane treatment from their employer may be set aside if it serves the broader interests of the community and society as a whole.

Employers may assume that the worker’s family will take care of their needs, thereby reducing or eliminating the employer’s responsibility.

6. Geography

GEOGRAPHY

Even geography-the physical location of a country and its relations with neighbors-can influence how that country views and practices corporate social responsibility.

For example, Poland lies along the fault line between Western Europe and Russia and the East. Over the past 20 years since the collapse of the USSR, Poland has gradually shifted its commercial and economic ties more toward the West, culminating in its accession to the European Union in 2004.

It is therefore unsurprising that CSR in Poland has taken on an increasingly Western character.

6. Geography

GEOGRAPHY

After the overthrow of the imperial regime in 1917, China’s political and economic systems were influenced by its northern neighbor, Russia. Similarly, the close economic and cultural ties between the United States and Canada, neighbors in North America, have shaped their shared perspectives on corporate social responsibility. The same argument can be made for neighboring countries in Northern Europe.

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These four elements of our analytical framework are **RELATIVELY STABLE** and therefore shape the very concept of corporate social responsibility in any country, region, or culture. The other four elements, however, are not as stable. As changes occur in a country's political structures, level of economic development, civil society institutions, and prevailing safety net provisions, the understanding and practice of CSR in that country evolves, as illustrated in the figure. We will now examine examples of these latter four elements.

7. Political Structures

POLITICAL STRUCTURES

Since corporate social responsibility is so closely linked to the relationship between business and government, it is easy to see why a country's political structures can influence the concept and practice of CSR in that country. A comparison between China and the United States, representing a communist form of governance and a predominantly capitalist political economy, offers a simple illustration and a striking contrast.

7. Political Structures

POLITICAL STRUCTURES

Since corporate social responsibility is so closely tied to the relationship between business and government, it is easy to see why a country’s political structures can shape the concept and practice of CSR there. A comparison between China and the United States-representing a communist form of governance and a predominantly capitalist political economy-offers a straightforward illustration and a vivid contrast.

7. Political Structures

POLITICAL STRUCTURES

The transition from Mao to Deng and the partial “opening” of China’s economy to market-based decisions has already been noted. This trend continued over the following three to four decades. Nevertheless, the Chinese government still directly or indirectly controls significant portions of its economy through state-owned enterprises (SOEs). The default position, so to speak, is that making economic decisions is a government function—except in those cases, places, and to the extent that the government chooses to relinquish control. China’s 1994 Company Law recognized the concept of corporate social responsibility.

7. Political Structures

POLITICAL STRUCTURES

This was made more explicit in Article 5 of the 2006 Company Law, which states: “In the course of doing business, a company shall comply with laws and administrative regulations, observe social morality and business ethics, act in good faith, accept government and public supervision, and bear social responsibility.” The nature and scope of this “social responsibility” remain unclear; to date, the Chinese government has paid considerably more attention to environmental issues than to human rights concerns. The clear implication is that CSR in China means whatever the government-i.e., the Communist Party-wants it to mean. One can only speculate whether the gradual increase in the number of Western multinational corporations (MNCs) operating in China will bring with it Western CSR concepts and practices.

7. Political Structures

POLITICAL STRUCTURES

In contrast, the default position in the United States and Western Europe is that the free market will make economic decisions, except in those areas where the government intervenes.

7. Political Structures

POLITICAL STRUCTURES

Thus, the political structures of any country influence the concept and practice of corporate social responsibility in three ways. First, there is the question of the extent to which the government or the free market makes economic decisions. Second, closely related to the first, is the question of how effective government regulation is. When safe and healthy working conditions are established by the government, it becomes less burdensome for corporations to manage their voluntary CSR practices. Third, there is the issue of the level of enforcement of such regulations. For example, China’s labor laws limit overtime work to no more than 36 hours per month, but Xu and Li (2013, p. 375) report that in 2010, during several reports of suicides, Foxconn employees were forced to work 80 to 100 hours of overtime per month. If enforcement of regulations is insufficient, the responsibility for humane treatment of employees again falls on the corporation.

Xu, K., & Li, W. (2013). An Ethical Stakeholder Approach to Crisis Communication: A Case Study of Foxconn’s 2010 Employee Suicide Crisis. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 117(2), 371–386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-012-1522-0>

Örtenblad, A. (2016). *Research Handbook on Corporate Social Responsibility in Context*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474806> p. 34

8. Level of Economic Development

LEVEL OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

It seems quite evident that a country's level of economic development will influence its views on corporate social responsibility, and this can be expressed on two levels: affordability and expectations. Returning to the issue of overtime work: can a poor country such as Bangladesh or the Central African Republic afford to impose a limited workweek for its citizens? If the country's role in international trade is based on its lowest wages, then from an economic, political, and social perspective, it may be impossible for either the government or the business community to take steps to limit allowable working hours and thereby raise wage rates. A developing country may simply not be able to afford the labor benefits that a developed country can provide-such as health insurance, paid leave, pension benefits, and more.

8. Level of Economic Development

LEVEL OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The question of expectations If the general population of a sub-Saharan African country is unfamiliar with the worker benefits mentioned above, businesses have little incentive to incur additional payroll costs. Kelsey Timmerman (2012) wrote that garment workers in Bangladesh resented human rights advocates' efforts to limit the number of overtime hours they were asked to work. They were not only accustomed to working 80 hours a week or more, but also wanted and needed the extra income.

Timmerman K. (2012) *Where am I wearing? A global tour to the countries, factories, and people that make our clothes* (2nd ed.). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons

8. Level of Economic Development

LEVEL OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

There are two additional aspects of economic development that may influence the practice of corporate social responsibility in a country: both are related to the DEGREE OF INDUSTRIALIZATION. By definition, CSR has little relevance to a country’s agricultural sector. Therefore, as a country’s economy grows and develops, and as manufacturing and services become more significant components of the overall economy, CSR also gains importance simply because corporations become more prominent players in that economy.

8. Level of Economic Development

LEVEL OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The second aspect stems from the LINK BETWEEN INDUSTRIALIZATION AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Rapid industrialization in China has led to well-documented and extremely serious air and water pollution problems. The central government has begun pushing the business sector to reduce dangerously high pollution levels, thereby increasing attention to CSR. In contrast, India's economy is still dominated by the agricultural sector. Corporate social responsibility is undoubtedly alive and well in India's academic institutions and corporate boardrooms, but it will become even more relevant and significant as the country's manufacturing sector grows and its agricultural sector declines as a percentage of the overall economy.

9. Civil Society Institutions

TRADE UNION ORGANIZATIONS

Since the mid-nineteenth century, when industrialization spread across much of the Western world and individual enterprises grew in wealth and power, the relationship between employers and their workers changed dramatically. An individual worker could not match the power of a giant corporation. Only by uniting in an organized way could workers expect to gain any bargaining power.

Broadly speaking, over the past 150 years trade unions in the developed world have played a role in three key areas, pressuring corporations to address the full range of worker concerns. **FIRST**, unions have applied pressure on employers through direct negotiations, using the threat of work stoppages to give themselves real leverage. **SECOND**, they have engaged in active political work—founding political parties in some countries (e.g., the United Kingdom) and supporting certain parties in others (e.g., the United States)—to secure legislative and regulatory backing for their members. **THIRD**, unions can influence broader society by drawing public attention to what they see as unfair wages and benefits or unsafe working conditions, thereby pressuring corporations to fulfill their responsibilities to employees.

9. Civil Society Institutions

ADVOCACY GROUPS / NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS

Another important institution in the civil society sector of any country is advocacy groups and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), which can be highly effective in raising corporate awareness of their responsibilities to various stakeholders. In the United States, at one end of the spectrum, there are literally dozens of privately funded environmental groups, independent of the government, working on a wide range of issues—from protecting endangered species, promoting more humane treatment in animal farming and slaughter for food, reducing carbon emissions, and safeguarding water supplies, to many other causes. Similarly, numerous human rights groups advocate for consumer rights, promote better corporate governance practices and shareholder rights, and monitor human rights issues in corporate supply chains.

9. Civil Society Institutions

At the other end of the spectrum, in developing countries in Africa, Asia, and South America, there are relatively few such local organizations. NGOs operating in these countries are more likely to be local branches of international organizations. Somewhere in the middle of the spectrum lies China. Under the communist regime, at least in theory, advocacy groups are unnecessary, as all political and economic activity is intended to serve the collective state. During Mao’s era, human rights groups were minimal in number and marginal in significance. However, over the past few decades, the number of such groups has increased from fewer than 5,000 in 1989 to 354,000 in 2006. Unlike in Western countries, these advocacy groups must obtain sponsorship from a government bureau to be legal, making them subject to government control rather than truly independent. Where advocacy groups and NGOs have a strong presence and enjoy independent status, they, much like trade unions, play a vital role in holding corporations accountable to a broad range of stakeholders. On their own, advocacy groups often have limited influence and power; their membership may be small, and their resources limited or uncertain. However, when they collaborate with media organizations, their impact and authority can grow substantially.

9. Civil Society Institutions

MEDIA

Too often in the West, we take strong and independent media for granted—print publications, broadcasting, and more recently, online platforms. We assume that media organizations, representing the full spectrum of political and economic ideologies—conservative, liberal, and everything in between—will openly and firmly express different viewpoints. Such an institution is absolutely essential for the full flourishing of corporate social responsibility.

TO THE EXTENT THAT COMPANY EXECUTIVES KNOW THEY CANNOT OPERATE BEHIND A VEIL OF SECRECY—AT LEAST NOT FOR LONG—AND THAT THEIR DECISIONS AND ACTIONS WILL INEVITABLY AND EVENTUALLY BE SUBJECT TO PUBLIC SCRUTINY, CORPORATE WRONGDOING IS MINIMIZED, AND CORPORATE RESPONSIBILITY IS ENCOURAGED.

The strength, freedom, and openness of these three civil society institutions—trade unions, advocacy groups, and the media—are crucial for understanding corporate social responsibility practices in any country. They represent an important aspect of the CSR “context.”

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10. 'SAFETY NET' PROVISIONS

The last of the eight elements in this analytical tool for understanding the context of corporate social responsibility in any country is the so-called safety net provisions that a country offers to those of its citizens who need them.

This once again underscores the important connection between business and government in the study and practice of CSR. Many countries in Western Europe, especially Germany and the Scandinavian countries, have fairly extensive “safety net” provisions, including, for example, supplemental food and housing assistance, public healthcare, unemployment insurance, early retirement, elder care, and childcare.

The United States is somewhat less generous but still offers many of these provisions to the unemployed or those out of work.

10. 'SAFETY NET' PROVISIONS

There are two completely different perspectives on how a country's social insurance system influences managers' understanding of their expectations and obligations regarding CSR.

The first can be described as a complementary relationship. If a country has a strong set of safety net provisions, it reflects the government's response to the wishes and expectations of its people. In such an environment, corporations are also likely to be responsive and to embrace their responsibilities toward various stakeholders.

The second can be described as an oppositional relationship. If a strong set of safety net provisions exists, corporations may assume their obligations are reduced because the need is smaller. Conversely, if the government provides less protection—for workers, consumers, or the environment—more responsibility falls on corporations.

Regardless of which perspective one favors, it is clear that safety net provisions are an important element in understanding perceptions and practices of corporate social responsibility in any country.

10. 'SAFETY NET' PROVISIONS

Thanks to this brief description of the eight elements of the tool for analyzing how CSR is perceived and practiced, it should now be clearer what the figure illustrates.

The first four elements—history, religions and philosophies, social norms, and geography—are static. They form the foundation for the concept of corporate social responsibility in a given country.

The last four elements—political structures, level of economic development, strength of trade unions, advocacy groups and free media, as well as the existence of social safety net provisions—can and do change.

For this reason, the perception and practice of CSR in each country is dynamic and evolving.

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The Conceptual Evolution of Corporate Social Responsibility: The Role of Context and Institutional Conditions

1. The Role of Context in the Evolution and Understanding of Corporate Social Responsibility
2. Conceptual Model of the Evolution and Development of Corporate Social Responsibility
3. History
4. Religion and Philosophical Traditions
5. Culture, Social Norms, and Customs
6. Geography
7. Political Structures
8. Level of Economic Development
9. Civil Society Institutions
10. Safety Networks

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**Topic 4. DIMENSIONS, KEY
CHARACTERISTICS, AND LEVELS OF
CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY**

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DIMENSIONS, KEY CHARACTERISTICS, AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR
2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR
3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AT THE MICRO LEVEL

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1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR

Five DIMENSIONS OF CSR

(Dahlsrud, 2008, p. 4)

Dimensions	The definition is coded to the dimension if it refers to	Example phrases
The environmental dimension	The natural environment	'a cleaner environment' 'environmental stewardship' 'environmental concerns in business operations'
The social dimension	The relationship between business and society	'contribute to a better society' 'integrate social concerns in their business operations' 'consider the full scope of their impact on communities'
The economic dimension	Socio-economic or financial aspects, including describing CSR in terms of a business operation	'contribute to economic development' 'preserving the profitability' 'business operations'
The stakeholder dimension	Stakeholders or stakeholder groups	'interaction with their stakeholders' 'how organizations interact with their employees, suppliers, customers and communities' 'treating the stakeholders of the firm'
The voluntariness dimension	Actions not prescribed by law	'based on ethical values' 'beyond legal obligations' 'voluntary'

Dahlsrud, A. (2008). How corporate social responsibility is defined: an analysis of 37 definitions. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 15(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.132>

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1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR

Five DIMENSIONS OF CSR

(Dahlsrud, 2008, p. 5)

Dimension	Dimension score	Dimension ratio (%)
The stakeholder dimension	1213	88
The social dimension	1213	88
The economic dimension	1187	86
The voluntariness dimension	1104	80
The environmental dimension	818	59

Dahlsrud, A. (2008). How corporate social responsibility is defined: an analysis of 37 definitions. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 15(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.132>

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1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR

Corporate political activity (CPA) has been linked to significant problems, such as agency costs for firms and the weakening of democratic institutions. 10.1016/j.jbusres.2023.113948

Corporate Social responsibility decoupling

Aspect	Description	Example
Definition	The gap between a company's CSR policies (what it says) and its actual CSR practices (what it does).	A company publicly commits to reducing CO ₂ emissions but continues to increase production in high-pollution facilities.
Types of Decoupling	Policy–Practice Decoupling – Promoting CSR policies without meaningful implementation. Means–Ends Decoupling – Implementing CSR activities, but they fail to achieve the intended outcomes.	Policy–Practice: Publishing a sustainability report without actual changes. Means–Ends: Launching recycling bins in offices, but waste is still sent to landfill.
Causes	Pressure to improve image, regulatory compliance without enforcement, lack of resources, conflicting business priorities.	A firm wants to appear “green” to investors but prioritizes cost-cutting over environmental action.
Consequences	Loss of trust, reputational damage, stakeholder backlash, potential legal or financial penalties.	NGO campaigns against a brand for false sustainability claims.
Prevention	Independent audits, stakeholder engagement, transparent reporting, measurable targets with verification.	Third-party verified carbon footprint reductions.

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1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR

ensuring good
historical coverage of
the field between
1953 and 2017

(Homer & Gill, 2022, p. 7)

Homer, S. T., & Gill, C. M. H. D. (2022).
How Corporate Social Responsibility Is
Described in Keywords: An Analysis of
144 CSR Definitions Across Seven
Decades. *Global Business Review*,
097215092211011.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509221101141>

Figure I. Number of CSR Definitions Published Annually.

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1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR

(Homer & Gill, 2022, p. 11)

Homer, S. T., & Gill, C. M. H. D. (2022). How Corporate Social Responsibility Is Described in Keywords: An Analysis of 144 CSR Definitions Across Seven Decades. *Global Business Review*, 097215092211011.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509221101141>

Figure 2. CSR Actors Keyword Groupings by Decade.

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1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR

(Homer & Gill, 2022, p. 11)

Homer, S. T., & Gill, C. M. H. D. (2022). How Corporate Social Responsibility Is Described in Keywords: An Analysis of 144 CSR Definitions Across Seven Decades. *Global Business Review*, 097215092211011.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509221101141>

Figure 3. CSR Actions Keyword Groupings by Decade.

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1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR

(Homer & Gill, 2022, p. 12)

Homer, S. T., & Gill, C. M. H. D. (2022). How Corporate Social Responsibility Is Described in Keywords: An Analysis of 144 CSR Definitions Across Seven Decades. *Global Business Review*, 097215092211011.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509221101141>

Figure 4. CSR Recipients Keyword Groupings by Decade.

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

Численні визначення КСВ пропонують науковці та коментатори, а також бізнес, громадянське суспільство, урядові та консультаційні організації. Загалом, визначення охоплюють такі ключові характеристики:

- відповідальність бізнесу перед суспільством (тобто підзвітність);
- відповідальність бізнесу перед та для суспільством (тобто за компенсацію негативних впливів і внесок у соціальний добробут);
- відповідальна поведінка в бізнесі (тобто бізнес має керуватися етично, відповідально та стабільно);
- відповідальність бізнесу перед суспільством і перед суспільством у широкому плані (тобто в тому числі екологічні проблеми); і
- управління бізнесом своїми відносинами із суспільством (Moon, 2014).

Moon, J. (2014). Corporate Social Responsibility: A Very Short Introduction. Oxford University Press.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/actrade/9780199671816.001.0001>

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

Ключові характеристики корпоративної соціальної відповідальності

Українською мовою	Англійською мовою
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • відповідальність бізнесу перед суспільством (тобто підзвітність); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • business responsibility to society (i.e., being accountable);
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • відповідальність бізнесу перед та для суспільством (тобто за компенсацію негативних впливів і внесок у соціальний добробут); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • business responsibility for society (i.e., in compensating for negative impacts and contributing to societal welfare);
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • відповідальна поведінка в бізнесі (тобто бізнес має керуватися етично, відповідально та стабільно); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • business responsible conduct (i.e., the business needs to be operated ethically, responsibly and sustainably);
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • відповідальність бізнесу перед суспільством і перед суспільством у широкому плані (тобто в тому числі екологічні проблеми); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • business responsibility to and for society in broad terms (i.e., including environmental issues);
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • управління бізнесом своїми відносинами із суспільством 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the management by business of its relationships with society.

Moon, J. (2014). Corporate Social Responsibility: A Very Short Introduction. Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/actrade/9780199671816.001.0001>

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

To facilitate the study of the relevance of these five points for organizations in different contexts, below is a slightly revised version of Moon's (2014) five points from the perspective of seven CSR aspects:

1. Being accountable
2. Compensating for one's own negative impacts
3. Compensating for the negative impacts of others
4. Contributing to societal well-being
5. Conducting business ethically, responsibly, and sustainably
6. Assuming responsibility for society and the environment in a broad sense
7. Managing business relationships with society

Örtenblad, A. (2016). Research Handbook on Corporate Social Responsibility in Context. Edward Elgar Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474806>

2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

Being accountable

Örtenblad, A. (2016). Research Handbook on Corporate Social Responsibility in Context. Edward Elgar Publishing.

<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474806> pp. 317–322

1. Being accountable

Explanation

Naturally, accountability is the most relevant concept for any company that wants to take the topic of CSR seriously. Borrowed from public administration and democratic governance theory, the **accountability of any societal actor to its constituency** forms the basis for the legitimacy of that actor's actions and existence. In the business world, as everyone knows, whenever any CSR-related message first appears anywhere in the world, it is addressed to so-called stakeholders. These are the parties entitled to demand justification from a business: shareholders, investors, employees, municipalities, government bodies, and citizens living near its factories, among others.

Thus, accountability means that companies must prove, explain, and justify certain actions to a range of stakeholders who, in turn, must demonstrate that their demands (i.e., their stakeholder status) are justified. This is a continuous, mutual process of verifying relationships with stakeholders, which may change over time: on one hand, employees cease to be stakeholders when they leave the company; investors cease to be stakeholders when they sell their shares in the firm. On the other hand, the theory and practice of democratic governance show that **the governance of any entity immediately ceases when its constituency withdraws trust in its legitimacy.**

In terms of CSR, this means that **companies cease to exist shortly after their stakeholders withdraw consent to what the company is doing.** Not all stakeholders have an immediate legal right to stop operations, but some do: legal bodies and courts that can revoke licenses and enforce their rulings; financiers who can withdraw funding; clients who can stop buying. In this light, **accountability, and therefore ensuring one's legitimacy, is a critical, vital legal safeguard for any business,** regardless of its sector, and is equally applicable to CSR matters. The issue in CSR is that companies recognize certain groups as stakeholders, whose opinions and right to express views must be respected and considered in decision-making.

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

2. Offsetting own negative impacts

Let us give an example of this aspect: in April 2013, the collapse of Rana Plaza, a commercial building in Savar, Bangladesh, where a number of textile factories produced garments for buyers around the world, cost the lives of more than a thousand workers. After the collapse, a cry of outrage echoed worldwide. In the ruins of Rana Plaza and among the bodies of the dead, journalists' cameras found and showed countless pieces of evidence of the responsibility of international brands: brand labels sewn onto garments made by workers in Rana Plaza. After the disaster, a tripartite agreement was concluded between the Government of Bangladesh, large garment manufacturing associations, and workers' representatives. As part of the arrangement, the Rana Plaza compensation fund was established, into which the government paid money. Ultimately, the inability of state authorities to effectively monitor the safety of Rana Plaza's building structure made them responsible for the collapse. The owner of Rana Plaza was also arrested. Although the government had not fulfilled its oversight obligations, this man broke laws, for example, by illegally adding unsafe upper floors to the building.

*Örtenblad, A. (2016).
Research Handbook on
Corporate Social
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Context. Edward Elgar
Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781783474806> pp.
317–322*

However, the largest contribution to the fund came from international brands: why, when they were neither owners, nor tenants, nor in any other way legally connected to the collapsed building? The only explanation that can be given is that a number of factories holding manufacturing contracts with them were tenants of Rana Plaza (and, incidentally, had forced their workers into the building despite seeing cracks in its structure). They paid several million dollars (exact figures for each contribution and the total amount can be found on the Rana Plaza Fund website). The point is that **international brands paid to offset a disaster that their stakeholders had directly or indirectly linked to their brands' responsibility**. They literally paid, dollar for dollar, unwillingly (though very reluctantly acknowledging) that this meant "offsetting their own negative consequences." This is an extraordinary case, and I cannot think of another in which the second of the six CSR aspects is illustrated so clearly.

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

3. Offsetting the negative impact of others

In light of what we mentioned in point 2, international brands that contributed to the Rana Plaza compensation fund firmly claim that the building's collapse did not fall within their zone of responsibility. Nevertheless, pressure from stakeholders forced them to pay. Thus, whether the negative impact is their own or someone else's, it is under the control of the stakeholder expressing their position, and the result of this argument is determined by the relative bargaining power held by that stakeholder.

Viewed through the lens of a world where CSR does not exist, the brands compensated for the negative impact caused by others (the reckless building owner or the unstructured government of Bangladesh). In a world where the CSR discourse exists – where legitimacy carries much more weight than legality in defining the boundaries of responsibility – the brands offset their own negative impact.

The stakeholders who compelled them to pay successfully used an argument against the brands: since you profited well while allowing your suppliers to manufacture under unsafe conditions, you bear responsibility for what happened. It is important to stress that **it is not the law, but the bargaining power of business stakeholders, spread across jurisdictions worldwide – just as supply chains stretch across the globe – that determines whether a negative impact on them is yours or someone else's.**

This situation arose from the global discussion on CSR, and it can no longer be viewed solely through the narrow lens of conventional business management.

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

4. Contribution to Social Welfare

For most businesses, there is no need to think specifically about CSR to make a contribution to social welfare. They contribute to social security by regularly paying wages to employees, taxes to government authorities, licensing fees to states, interest to banks, and payments to suppliers. This is only the financial side. Companies also promote social welfare by developing and implementing technologies, educating people, and thereby spreading innovation and fostering societal development. In a society based on work and wages, work means more than just money: it is a calling that gives meaning and motivation to a person's life.

Therefore, business does not necessarily have to think about CSR to contribute to social welfare. In Germany, people often refer to the famous *Mittelstand*. Millions of small and medium-sized enterprises of the *Mittelstand* form the backbone of the German economy. These companies are part of society, ensuring important preconditions for social order, such as identity and group cohesion. Thus, companies are undoubtedly not entities outside society that do something for it, as is sometimes argued in CSR discussions. They are a far more integral part of the constellation of public and private institutions. Naturally, companies can always decide to do more or less. Those that do less will cite economic reasoning; those that do more will call it CSR.

*Örtenblad, A. (2016).
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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

5. Conducting business ethically, responsibly, and sustainably

If you claim to be a responsible actor in society – whether you are a business, a local or national government entity, an association, or a non-governmental organization – you will, of course, act ethically, responsibly, and sustainably. Responsibility, as stated above, is not an absolute term but depends on the authority of stakeholders to define the boundaries of responsibility. It is the result of negotiating power in arenas that may include players from just one village or, at times, from the global village.

As for ethics, in this specific CSR context, let me suggest that it refers to the goods and services produced by the monitored enterprise. We see no value to any society in CSR efforts of any kind in the case of the arms industry or the tobacco industry. Both operate at society's expense, and these costs cannot be offset by any other measure except withdrawal from the market. Of course, there is a wide grey area where the situation is not so clear-cut.

This brings us to sustainability. To achieve a more sustainable world (without modestly claiming a “fully sustainable world”), all actors must be engaged. In our view, CSR can be seen as the business sector's contribution to sustainable development. Much more still needs to be done – for example, in energy use, emissions, product life cycles, product design (to address the environmental dimension of sustainability) – as well as in fair business practices and meeting stakeholder requirements (to address the social dimension of sustainability).

Remember: the economic dimension of sustainability means that, while moving towards the other two dimensions, enterprises must operate profitably to stay in the game.

The “Magna Carta” of sustainable development is the **Rio de Janeiro Declaration** of 1992, supplemented by **Agenda 21**, which outlines recommendations on how to follow the path of sustainable development.

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

5. Conducting business ethically, responsibly, and sustainably

However, since then, the CSR discourse has overshadowed the consumer side of sustainability. I recall focus groups as part of local Agenda 21 processes, where citizens came together to discuss what they could contribute to this issue. The results of these discussions were often very simple, practical proposals – such as forming car-sharing groups, buying food from local farms, or using public transport. But what happened to that?

I have the impression that, in the course of CSR discussions, the dual challenge of sustainable production and consumption has been split, making it convenient to lean back and demand action solely from the production side. Perhaps I am going too far, but I firmly believe that the sustainable consumption side needs to return to the picture for sustainable development to remain a meaningful concept.

Take the example mentioned above of the global textile industry (often considered unsustainable). Manufacturers in Bangladesh constantly claim that the prices paid by buyers are insufficient to pay fair wages, create safe conditions, and keep the business running. Buyers, in turn, argue that consumers will not agree to higher retail prices. And what do consumers say (and do)?

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

6. Taking responsibility for society and the environment in a broad sense:

We will not repeat ourselves on the topic of responsibility. In a broad sense, in our view, this means interaction with stakeholders at the macro level – whether to address issues in the social or environmental sphere. And, to be honest, it is often difficult to distinguish this from... the next point 7.

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

7. Managing Business Relationships with Society

It is worth noting, however, that stakeholder relationship management at the macro level has changed significantly over the past decades. The essential task of managing relationships with stakeholders — from the perspective of legitimacy, as outlined above - was approached very differently by businesses in the past. One of the defining factors appears to have been the macro-conditions of the political economy in which companies operate.

At one end of the spectrum are liberal market economies, where relationships between firms and other actors are coordinated primarily through markets. At the other end are coordinated market economies, where companies typically engage in more strategic, long-term relationships with stakeholders such as trade unions, suppliers, and banks.

It can be argued that in each case, business acts in a way that complements the characteristics of the political economy: in coordinated market economies, all stakeholders were generally included in arbitration processes over interests, which took place at supervisory board meetings.

In a typical German publicly listed company in the 1980s, the supervisory board included representatives from the financial sector, one from trade unions, one representing state or municipal administration, and often even representatives from companies in the same line of business. CSR as a concept was unknown in such supervisory board structures, because coordinated market economies were so deeply intertwined that stakeholders negotiated behind closed doors in boardrooms.

Since multiple reciprocal relationships between business, trade unions, the state, finance, and interest groups were the norm, the CSR discourse was absent.

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2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR

7. Managing Business Relationships with Society

Look for a similar case in “Japan Inc.,” which operated in much the same way as “Deutschland AG.” By contrast, in more liberal forms of market economy, such as the Anglo-American model, the level of interdependence was generally lower. Coordination between systems relied primarily on markets, with supervisory institutions ensuring that markets functioned effectively. In such a system, the practice of mutual legitimization among stakeholders was absent, and other forms of legitimizing business had to be sought.

Therefore, I argue that it is no coincidence that the CSR debate has existed in the Anglo-Saxon world since at least the 1960s: it was first mentioned by the American Clarence C. Walton in 1967 (Walton, 1967). If you consider the dramatic shifts brought by globalization, along with economic globalization over the past 25 years, the pendulum has clearly swung toward more liberal forms of coordination within political economies.

As a result, the CSR discussion has arrived on the continent to stay in play. The task of managing business relationships with society has fundamentally changed. It has changed in terms of management: procedures for arbitrating interests with societal stakeholders have been displaced from boardrooms into the media, social networks, and “multiple stakeholder” forums.

Moreover, it has changed from society’s perspective: today stakeholders are scattered across the globe and countless jurisdictions - society is now global, albeit a fragmented global society. CSR, in our view, is a global discourse within which the critical and vital coordination of interests between business and its stakeholders is tested, adapted, and readapted to ensure the legitimacy of the global social institution called “business.”

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3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Castelló & Lozano (2009) developed a staged model of corporate social responsibility, as shown in the figure (Castelló & Lozano, 2009).

Adapted CSR Maturity Model (Castelló & Lozano, 2009, p. 331)

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3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Stage 1. RISK MANAGEMENT.

This is the basic stage, where corporate social responsibility is seen as a tool to protect the value of reputation. Within risk management, companies begin developing systems to measure and control environmental and social issues and threats. These control systems involve planning and social forecasting, preparing for social responses, and developing the first set of corporate social policies.

Stage 2. INTEGRATED POSITION.

Responsibility management. Companies modify their business processes and control mechanisms to reflect social and environmental responsibility. The management of social issues becomes proactive and systematic, often through the use of widely recognized performance standards. A change in the power structure is often required, leading to the creation of corporate social responsibility departments.

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3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Stage 3. CORPORATE CITIZENSHIP.

Civil governance. At this stage, the company focuses on its role as a corporate citizen. It is open to integrating social issues as part of its obligations, assuming the role of citizenship in leading social matters and transforming its business models to achieve this goal. This transformation is often driven by an internal redefinition of the company's role, mission, and vision toward the values of corporate social responsibility. Programs with broad scope and depth of responsibility often stimulate social innovations that benefit both the firm and the communities in which it operates. Management systems are designed to monitor goals related to improving environmental and social impact.

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3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Which CSR position do companies occupy today?

The answer depends on which regions of the world and industries are being analyzed. Mirvis & Googins (2006) argue that looking at the rankings of the 100 largest U.S. companies seems to show that the average company is somewhere between what these authors call Stage 2 (“Engaged”) and Stage 3 (“Innovative”)-which Castelló & Lozano (2009) refer to as “Risk Management” and “Integrated Position.”

Examples such as GE, IBM, CEMEX, and transformations like those undergone by Nike illustrate how business understanding of CSR evolves. It is also important to remember the permeability of the boundaries drawn around different positions and the need to view the proposed framework from a dynamic perspective.

Mirvis, P., & Googins, B. (2006). Stages of Corporate Citizenship. California Management Review, 48(2), 104–126.

<https://doi.org/10.2307/41166340>

Castelló, I., & Lozano, J. (2009). From risk management to citizenship corporate social responsibility: analysis of strategic drivers of change. Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society, 9(4), 373–385.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/14720700910984927>

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3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Instead of thinking about knowledge management, “stage-based” thinking offers an evolutionary approach, where the future is built on the past rather than on a path that diverges from it. Rather than assuming that what was done in the past was wrong, past actions are the only available foundation for future actions. If past actions are not on the path to success, the direction changes without altering history (Örtenblad, 2016, p. 334).

Based on the modeling approach in this section, there are several possible alternatives to Castelló and Lozano (2009). One option is presented in the figure, which shows a four-stage model by Örtenblad, 2016:

CSR Maturity Levels Model (Örtenblad, 2016, p. 334)

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3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Level I. Business stage of maximizing profit for owners within the corporate mission.

At this basic maturity level, the company is concerned only with itself and its owners. In addition, the company seeks to satisfy its customers so that they continue to purchase its goods and services. The sole responsibility of corporations is to maximize profit for shareholders within open and free competition, without deception or fraud. Making decisions that serve other interests at the expense of shareholder profit would mean breaching trust and loyalty. It would be like taking money from the owners and would resemble theft. According to this view, company executives have no right to act like modern-day Robin Hoods, taking money from the rich and giving it to the poor.

Level II. Functional stage of creating a corporate social responsibility (CSR) function in the company.

At this second maturity level, business leaders have realized that they need to professionally manage the company's relations with the outside world. Given the need and external expectations, the company creates a CSR function, staffed by individuals with a business perspective. The function here involves researching the consequences of business activities in the external environment; developing intelligence to learn about external reactions to business practices; and conducting risk assessments in terms of their impact on corporate reputation. At this level, CSR is defined as a process. The process implies that corporate leaders in the organization reflect on and discuss relationships with stakeholders and partners. This process also requires corporate leaders to define their own role and the role of the organization in relation to social conditions and public benefit. This kind of reflection and discussion will lead them to give their roles appropriate meaning and action.

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Level III. Resource stage of mobilizing resources for potential threats and opportunities.

At this level, we see a complete but passive form of corporate social responsibility. It is a response strategy, in which the company mobilizes resources in case of emergencies. The company is prepared for crisis management as well as for identifying and seizing opportunities. Opportunities may arise when corporate executives engage in opportunistic behavior to take advantage of situations in terms of strengthening corporate reputation. CSR at this level is a concept that compels the company to integrate the principles of social and environmental responsibility and encourages participation in the company's activities, both internal and external.

From this definition, two perspectives follow. First, CSR implies a strong connection with internal business processes; second, interaction with stakeholders and society at large also requires the involvement of stakeholders and society as a whole in terms of their relationship with the company.

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3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Level IV. Contribution stage of active engagement with society.

At this final level of maturity, company executives, as well as all other members of the organization, perceive their business as part of a greater cause in society. They take on comprehensive and active responsibility both in the local and global community, seeking opportunities where the company can make a difference. At this level of CSR, short-term losses for the company may be acceptable when compared to long-term benefits for society. CSR here is a long-term commitment to society (Mostovicz et al., 2009). There is evidence that long-term civic commitments by a company should in no way harm corporate profitability-neither in the short nor in the long term.

Mostovicz, I., Kakabadse, N., & Kakabadse, A. (2009). CSR: the role of leadership in driving ethical outcomes. Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society, 9(4), 448–460. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14720700910984990>

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DIMENSIONS, KEY CHARACTERISTICS, AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

- 1. DIMENSIONS OF CSR**
- 2. KEY CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF CSR**
- 3. STAGES AND LEVELS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AT THE MICRO LEVEL**

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Topic 5. GENERATIONS AND
STAGES OF CORPORATE SOCIAL
RESPONSIBILITY

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GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

1. GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CSR
2. THE TRIPLE CURSE OF MODERN CSR
3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0
4. CSR 1.0 VS CSR 2.0: MACRO AND MICRO LEVELS
5. THE DNA OF CSR 2.0
6. CSR 3.0 AND 4.0

1. GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CSR

Table 1: The Ages and Stages of CSR

<i>Economic Age</i>	<i>Stage of CSR</i>	<i>Modus Operandi</i>	<i>Key Enabler</i>	<i>Stakeholder Target</i>
Greed	Defensive	Ad hoc interventions	Investments	Shareholders, government & employees
Philanthropy	Charitable	Charitable programmes	Projects	Communities
Marketing	Promotional	Public relations	Media	General public
Management	Strategic	Management systems	Codes	Shareholders & NGOs/CSOs
Responsibility	Systemic	Business models	Products	Regulators & customers

Visser, W. considers it useful to view the evolution of business responsibility in terms of five overlapping periods - the ages of greed, philanthropy, marketing, management, and responsibility - each typically demonstrating a different stage of CSR: defensive, charitable, promotional, strategic, and systemic. Visser, W. argues that companies generally pass through these milestones and stages (although they may operate in several ages and stages simultaneously) and that we should encourage business to transition toward systemic CSR. If companies remain at any of the first four stages, “we will fail to reverse the course of the environmental, social, and ethical crises we face. Put simply, CSR will continue to fail” (Visser, W. V., 2011, p. 2).

1. GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CSR

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Responsibility	Systemic	Business models	Products	Regulators & customers

The **Age of Greed** is characterized by *defensive CSR*, in which all corporate sustainability and responsibility practices - usually limited in scope — are applied only when it can be demonstrated that doing so will **protect shareholder value**.

Thus, employee volunteer programs (linked to higher staff motivation, loyalty, and productivity) are not uncommon, as well as targeted expenditures (e.g., on pollution control) perceived as a shield against regulation or a way to avoid fines and penalties.

1. GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CSR

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Philanthropic CSR in the era of philanthropy refers to a company’s support of various social and environmental initiatives through donations and sponsorship, usually via a foundation, trust, or the chairperson’s fund, aimed at empowering community groups or civil society organizations.

Promotional CSR in the era of marketing occurs when corporate sustainability and responsibility are viewed primarily as a public relations opportunity to enhance the company’s brand, image, and reputation. Promotional CSR may build on philanthropic and strategic CSR practices, transforming them into PR campaigns often described as *greenwashing*.

1. GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CSR

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Responsibility	Systemic	Business models	Products	Regulators & customers

Strategic CSR, which emerged in the era of management, refers to linking CSR activities to the company’s core business (for example, Coca-Cola’s focus on water resource management), often through adherence to CSR codes and the implementation of social and environmental management systems. These systems typically include cycles of CSR policy development, setting goals and objectives, implementing programs, conducting audits, and reporting.

Systemic CSR in the era of responsibility focuses its efforts on identifying and eliminating the root causes of our current instability and irresponsibility, usually through innovative business models, the transformation of processes, products, and services, and advocacy for progressive national and international policies. Thus, while strategic CSR is focused on the micro level-supporting social or environmental issues that align with the company’s strategy (but do not necessarily change that strategy)-systemic CSR focuses on understanding macro-level system interconnections-society and ecosystems-and adapting the strategy to optimize outcomes for this broader human and ecological system.

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2. THE TRIPLE CURSE OF MODERN CSR

Curse 1: CSR Incrementalism

One of the greatest revolutions of the 1970s was total quality management, conceived by American statistician W. Edwards Deming and perfected by the Japanese before being exported worldwide as ISO 9001. At the core of Deming's TQM model and the ISO standard lies the principle of continuous improvement, which has now become pervasive across all management system approaches to performance. It is therefore no surprise that the most popular environmental management standard, ISO 14001, is built on the same principle.

There is nothing inherently wrong with continuous improvement. On the contrary, it has brought safety and reliability to the very products and services we associate with modern quality of life. However, when we use it as the primary approach to solving our social, environmental, and ethical problems, it fails for two critical reasons: **speed** and **scale**. The incremental approach to CSR, though rich in evidence of micro-scale, gradual improvements, has had absolutely no impact on the large-scale sustainability crises we face—many of which are worsening at rates far exceeding any feeble attempts at CSR improvement.

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2. THE TRIPLE CURSE OF MODERN CSR

Curse 2: Peripheral CSR

Ask any CSR manager what frustrates them most, and they will tell you: the lack of top management commitment. This is “code” for saying that CSR is, at best, a peripheral function in most companies. There may be a CSR manager, even a CSR department, a CSR report, and public commitments to any number of CSR codes and standards. But this does little to conceal the fundamental truth that **shareholder-driven capitalism is rampant**, and its obsession with short-term financial performance is in almost every respect at odds with the long-term stakeholder approach required for high-impact CSR.

The collapse of Enron, and the reason our current financial crisis was allowed to spiral out of control, lay not in a few rogue executives or creative accounting, but in a culture of greed embedded in the corporate DNA and financial markets. Whether you agree or not (and despite new research on “responsible competitiveness”), it is hard to find any significant examples where financial markets consistently reward responsible behavior.

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2. THE TRIPLE CURSE OF MODERN CSR

Curse 3: Non-Economic CSR

If there has ever been a monotonously repeated, stuck record in the CSR debate, it is about the so-called “*business case*” for CSR. This stems from the fact that CSR managers, consultants, and sometimes even CEOs desperately seek convincing evidence that “*doing good is good for business*”-in other words, that CSR pays off. The lack of supporting research does not seem to deter these enthusiasts, who endlessly chant the business-case mantra as though it were self-evident truth.

A far more *inconvenient truth* is that CSR sometimes pays off, under certain circumstances-but more often, it does not. Of course, there are low-hanging fruits, such as eco-efficiency in waste and energy, but these only go so far. Most of the radical CSR changes needed to address poverty and the ongoing sixth mass extinction of species require strategic shifts and substantial investment. They may very well be profitable in the long term and economically rational over one or two generations, but-as we have already established-financial markets simply do not operate that way, at least not yet.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

The emergence of CSR 2.0

In contrast, when we enter the era of responsibility, systemic CSR, or CSR 2.0, can be characterized by five principles:

1. Creativity
2. Scalability
3. Responsiveness
4. Locality
5. Circularity

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

Creativity

To succeed in the CSR revolution, we will need innovation and creativity. From Thomas Kuhn's *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, we know that transformative change occurs only when we can reconceive our world - when we can discover a truly new paradigm or model of thinking. This process of "creative destruction" is now a widely accepted theory of social change, first introduced by German sociologist Werner Sombart and later developed and popularized by Austrian economist Joseph Schumpeter. To paraphrase Einstein, we cannot solve today's problems with yesterday's thinking.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

Creativity

Business is inherently creative and innovative. The Age of Responsibility differs in that business creativity should be directed toward addressing global social and environmental challenges. Apple, for example, is highly creative, yet the iPhone does little to tackle our most pressing societal needs.

In contrast, Vodafone's M-PESA innovation by Safaricom in Kenya, which enables money transfers via text messages, has expanded opportunities in a country where 80% of the population lacks bank accounts and where more funds enter through international remittances than through foreign aid.

<https://www.thefastmode.com/investments-and-expansions/32060-safaricom-receives-approval-to-launch-m-pesa-in-ethiopia>

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

Creativity

Consider, for example, Freeplay's innovation of using battery-free technology for torches, radios, and laptops in Africa, thereby providing millions of people with access to products and services in regions disconnected from the power grid.

All of this is part of the exciting trend toward social entrepreneurship or social business that is spreading worldwide.

It is not a cure-all, but for certain products and services, directing business creativity toward society's most urgent needs is the fastest and most scalable way to enter the Age of Responsibility.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

2. Scalability

CSR literature is filled with charming case studies of genuinely responsible and sustainable projects and a handful of pioneering companies. The problem is that so few of them ever achieve scale. It is almost as if, once the sound bites and PR applause have been secured, no further action is needed. They remain as impressive pilot projects and best practice examples, tainted only by the fact that they are endlessly repeated at CSR conferences worldwide, with no vision of how they could transform the core business of their originators.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

2. Scalability

The sustainable development challenges we face - whether climate change or poverty - are of such enormous scale and urgency that any CSR solutions failing to match that scale and urgency are, at best, distractions and, at worst, harmful. How long have we indulged in ethical consumerism (organic, fair trade, etc.) that has had almost no impact on major global corporations or supply chains?

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

3. Responsiveness

Business has a long track record of responding to community needs - witness generations of philanthropy and touching generosity after disasters and emergencies. But this responsiveness has often been on their own terms, giving when it is easy, and writing checks without disrupting the commercial side of the business. The seriousness of the global issues we face requires companies to go much further. CSR 2.0 demands an uncomfortable, transformational responsiveness that questions whether the industry or the business model itself is part of the solution - or part of the problem.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

3. Responsiveness

When it became clear that climate change posed a serious threat to the stability of the fossil fuel industry, all major oil companies formed the Global Climate Coalition, a lobbying group aimed at discrediting and denying the science of climate change and undermining key international efforts in this area - notably the Kyoto Protocol.

In typical CSR 1.0 style, these same companies simultaneously made hollow statements about their CSR. In contrast, the Prince of Wales's Corporate Leaders Group on Climate Change has, since 2005, lobbied for bolder UK, EU, and international climate legislation, recognizing the need to cut carbon emissions by 50-85% by 2050.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

4. Glocality

The term “glocalization” comes from the Japanese word *dochakuka*, which simply means “global localization.” Originally referring to the adaptation of agricultural technologies to local conditions, *dochakuka* evolved into a marketing strategy adopted by Japanese businesspeople in the 1980s. It was later introduced and popularized in the West in the 1990s.

In the CSR context, the idea of “think globally, act locally” recognizes that most CSR issues appear as dilemmas rather than easy choices. In a complex, interconnected world, CSR 2.0 requires companies (and their critics) to become far more sophisticated in understanding local conditions and finding appropriate local solutions, while still adhering to universal principles.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

4. Glocality

For example, a few years ago BHP Billiton was outraged by its relatively poor performance in the (then) *Business in the Environment* (BiE) index, run by the UK charity *Business in the Community*. Further analysis revealed that the company's scores were lowered due to high energy consumption and relatively low energy efficiency.

At the time, most of BHP Billiton's operations were located in southern Africa, where electricity was among the cheapest in the world. It was therefore not a priority. However, combating malaria in the communities where they operated was a priority, and they had made a significant positive impact in this area. Yet the BiE index had no questions in its ranking related to malaria, so this was ignored. Instead, it demonstrated the typical, Western-driven, one-size-fits-all approach of CSR 1.0.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

4. Glocality

Carroll's CSR pyramid has already been mentioned. However, a sugar cooperative in Guatemala has its own CSR pyramid - economic responsibility remains the base, but instead of legal, ethical, and philanthropic aspects, their pyramid includes responsibility to the family (of employees), the community, and participation in politics. Clearly, both Carroll's pyramid and the Guatemalan pyramid are valuable in their respective contexts. Thus, CSR 2.0 replaces "either/or" thinking with a "both/and" approach.

CSR 2.0 seeks the Chinese concept of a harmonious society, which envisions a dynamic but productive tension between opposites.

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

5. Circularity

The reason CSR 1.0 failed lies not in the absence of good intentions, nor even in the lack of effort. Old CSR collapsed because our global economic system is built on a fundamentally flawed design. Despite all the miraculous energy unleashed by Adam Smith's "invisible hand" of the free market, our modern capitalist system is defective at its very core. Simply put, it is conceived AS AN ABSTRACT SYSTEM WITHOUT LIMITS.

Back in the 1960s, pioneering economist Kenneth Boulding called this the "cowboy economy," where infinite frontiers assume no limits on resource consumption or waste disposal. In contrast, he argued, we must design a "spaceship economy," where there is no "away"; everything is created for continuous recycling.

1. Boulding, K. (1966). *The Economics of the Coming Spaceship Earth*. Resources for the Future, pp. 1 -

14. http://arachnid.biosci.utexas.edu/courses/THOC/Readings/Boulding_SpaceshipEarth.pdf

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3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0

Emergence of CSR 2.0

5. Circularity

In the 1990s, in *The Ecology of Commerce*, Paul Hawken translated these ideas into three basic rules of sustainable development:

1. Waste equals food.
2. Nature runs on current solar income.
3. Nature depends on diversity.

He also proposed replacing our product sales economy with a service leasing model, using the famous example of Interface's "Evergreen" carpets, which are leased, continually replaced, and recycled. William McDonough and Michael Braungart expanded this thinking in their *Cradle to Cradle* industrial model. Cradle to Cradle is not only about closing the production loop; it is about designing for "what is good" rather than following CSR 1.0's principle of "less bad."

Hawken P. (2010) *The Ecology of Commerce Revised Edition: A Declaration of Sustainability* (Collins Business Essentials) <https://www.amazon.com/Ecology-Commerce-Revised-Declaration-Sustainability/dp/0061252794>

Visser, W. V. (2011). *The Ages and Stages of CSR: Towards the Future with CSR 2.0*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc

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4. CSR 1.0 VS CSR 2.0: MACRO AND MICRO LEVELS

Emergence of CSR 2.0

Shifts will occur on two levels.

At the macro level, there will be changes in the ontological assumptions or worldviews of CSR.

At the micro level, there will be changes in the methodological practices of CSR or the ways of being in the world.

Hawken P. (2010) *The Ecology of Commerce Revised Edition: A Declaration of Sustainability* (Collins Business Essentials) <https://www.amazon.com/Ecology-Commerce-Revised-Declaration-Sustainability/dp/0061252794>

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4. CSR 1.0 VS CSR 2.0: MACRO AND MICRO LEVELS

Changes at the macro level can be described as follows:

1. Paternalistic relationships between companies and the community, based on philanthropy, will give way to more equal partnerships.
2. Defensive, minimalist responses to social and environmental issues will be replaced by proactive strategies and investments in growing responsibility markets, such as clean technologies.
3. CSR approaches focused on reputation will no longer be trusted, and companies will be evaluated on actual social, environmental, and ethical performance — that is, whether conditions on the ground are improving in absolute, cumulative terms.
4. While CSR specialists will still play a role, every aspect of CSR 2.0 performance will be embedded and integrated into the core operations of companies.
5. Standardized approaches will remain useful as consensus benchmarks, but CSR will find diverse expression and implementation at very local levels.
6. CSR-related decisions, including responsible products and services, will shift from niche “nice-to-haves” to “must-haves” for the mass market.
7. The entire CSR concept will lose its Western conceptual and operational dominance, giving way to a more culturally diverse and internationally applicable concept.

MACRO	
CSR 1.0	CSR 2.0
Philanthropic	Collaborative
Risk-based	Reward-based
Image-driven	Performance-driven
Specialized	Integrated
Standardized	Diversified
Marginal	Scalable
Western	Global

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4. CSR 1.0 VS CSR 2.0: MACRO AND MICRO LEVELS

Expected changes at the micro level can be described as follows:

- 1.CSR will no longer be manifested as luxury-class products and services (as in current “green” and fair trade variants), but as affordable solutions for those most in need of quality-of-life improvements.
- 2.Preference will shift toward investments in self-sustaining social enterprises rather than cheque-book philanthropy.
- 3.CSR indices that repeatedly rank the same large companies (often revealing contradictions between indices) will give way to CSR rating systems that convert social, environmental, ethical, and economic performance into corporate grades (A+, B-, etc., similar to credit ratings), which analysts and others can use for decision-making.
- 4.Trust in CSR departments will fade or dissipate as responsibility- and sustainability-related performance becomes increasingly embedded into corporate performance assessments and market incentive systems.
- 5.Voluntary ethical consumer choices will become irrelevant as CSR 2.0 companies begin to edit choices - that is, stop offering implicitly “less ethical” product ranges, thereby enabling guilt-free purchasing.
- 6.Post-use product responsibility will become obsolete as the service rental and take-back economy becomes mainstream.
- 7.Annual CSR reporting will be replaced by real-time online CSR performance data streams.
- 8.These live communications will be fueled by social networks connected to Web 2.0, enabling “crowdsourcing” instead of periodic meetings with cumbersome stakeholder groups.
- 9.Typical CSR 1.0 management system standards, such as ISO 14001, will be less robust than new performance standards, such as those emerging around climate change, which set absolute limits and thresholds.

MICRO	
CSR premium	Base of the pyramid
Charity projects	Social enterprise
CSR indexes	CSR ratings
CSR departments	CSR incentives
Product liability	Choice editing
Ethical consumerism	Service agreements
CSR reporting cycles	CSR data streams
Stakeholder groups	Social networks
Process standards	Performance standards

Visser, W. V. (2011). *The Ages and Stages of CSR: Towards the Future with CSR 2.0*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc

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5. CSR 2.0 DNA

CSR 2.0 DNA

Bringing it all together, CSR 2.0 represents a new, holistic CSR model. The essence of the CSR 2.0 DNA model lies in four bases of responsibility. In the case of CSR 2.0, the DNA bases of responsibility are:

1. Value creation,
2. Good governance,
3. Societal contribution, and
4. Environmental integrity.

DNA Code	Strategic Goals	Key Indicators
Value creation	Economic development	Capital investment (financial, manufacturing, social, human & natural capital) Beneficial products (sustainable & responsible goods & services) Inclusive business (wealth distribution, bottom of the pyramid markets)
Good governance	Institutional effectiveness	Leadership (strategic commitment to sustainability & responsibility) Transparency (sustainability & responsibility reporting, government payments) Ethical practices (bribery & corruption prevention, values in business)
Societal contribution	Stakeholder orientation	Philanthropy (charitable donations, provision of public goods & services) Fair labour practices (working conditions, employee rights, health & safety) Supply chain integrity (SME empowerment, labour & environmental standards)
Environmental integrity	Sustainable ecosystems	Ecosystem protection (biodiversity conservation & ecosystem restoration) Renewable resources (tackling climate change, renewable energy & materials) Zero waste production (cradle-to-cradle processes, waste elimination)

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5. CSR 2.0 DNA

CSR 2.0 DNA – VALUE CREATION

When we look at value creation, it is clear that we are talking about more than just financial profitability. The goal is economic development, which means not only enriching shareholders and executives but also improving the economic context in which the company operates, including investments in infrastructure, job creation, and skills development.

Key performance indicators can be as many as you wish, but I want to highlight two that I consider important:

- Useful products
- Inclusive business

Do the company’s products and services truly improve our quality of life, or do they cause harm or add to what Charles Handy calls the “society of chindogu” - low-quality junk? And how are the economic benefits distributed? Does wealth flow upwards or downwards? Are workers, SMEs in the supply chain, and poor communities truly empowered?

Visser, W. V. (2011). *The Ages and Stages of CSR: Towards the Future with CSR 2.0*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc

DNA Code	Strategic Goals	Key Indicators
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CHINDOGU – The Japanese Art of Unuseless Inventions

<https://iii.org.za/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/iii-ART-CHINDOGU-CJM-2.pdf>

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5. CSR 2.0 DNA

CSR 2.0 DNA – GOOD GOVERNANCE

Good governance is another area that is not new but has not been properly recognized or integrated into CSR. Institutional effectiveness is as important as higher social and environmental ideals. Ultimately, if an institution fails or lacks transparency and fairness, it undermines everything CSR aims to achieve. Trends in reporting, as well as other forms of transparency such as social media and public CSR performance databases linked to brands or products, will become increasingly important measures of success, alongside embedding ethical behavior into corporate culture.

Tools such as Goodguide, KPMG’s Integrity Thermometer, and the EthicalQuote Covalence ranking will become more widespread.

DNA Code	Strategic Goals	Key Indicators
Value creation	Economic development	Capital investment (financial, manufacturing, social, human & natural capital) Beneficial products (sustainable & responsible goods & services) Inclusive business (wealth distribution, bottom of the pyramid markets)
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<https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/ch/pdf/ch-integrity-thermometer-en.pdf>

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5. CSR 2.0 DNA

CSR 2.0 DNA - SOCIAL CONTRIBUTION

Social contribution is an area to which CSR has traditionally paid more attention, with its goal being stakeholder orientation. This gives philanthropy its rightful place in CSR - as one tile in a larger mosaic - while also highlighting the importance of fair labor practices. It is simply unacceptable that there are more people in slavery today than before it was officially abolished in the 1800s, just as the regular exposure of well-known companies for using child labor is disgraceful. This area of stakeholder engagement, community participation, and supply chain integrity remains one of the most troubling and critical elements of CSR.

DNA Code	Strategic Goals	Key Indicators
Value creation	Economic development	Capital investment (financial, manufacturing, social, human & natural capital) Beneficial products (sustainable & responsible goods & services) Inclusive business (wealth distribution, bottom of the pyramid markets)
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<https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/ch/pdf/ch-integrity-thermometer-en.pdf>

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5. CSR 2.0 DNA

CSR 2.0 DNA - ENVIRONMENTAL INTEGRITY

Environmental integrity sets the bar higher than merely minimizing harm; it aims instead to sustain and enhance ecosystem resilience.

Key performance indicators give some sense of the level of ambition required here - 100% renewable energy and zero waste.

We cannot continue the same practices that, according to WWF's Living Planet Index, have resulted in the loss of one-third of the planet's biodiversity since monitoring began in 1970.

Nor can we continue to risk the prospect of dangerous - and potentially catastrophic and irreversible - climate change.

DNA Code	Strategic Goals	Key Indicators
Value creation	Economic development	Capital investment (financial, manufacturing, social, human & natural capital) Beneficial products (sustainable & responsible goods & services) Inclusive business (wealth distribution, bottom of the pyramid markets)
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<https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/ch/pdf/ch-integrity-thermometer-en.pdf>

6. DNA of CSR 3.0 and CSR 4.0

CSR 3.0

According to Dumont (2012), CSR 3.0 engages communities across geographic, age, and socio-economic boundaries, reducing delay times, maintaining stakeholder interest, and assuming responsibility.

In the proposed **CSR 4.0 framework**, Munro (2020) argues that it is necessary to change the way organizations and companies operate and conduct business within the development of CSR and a shared and integrated environment. Key principles and themes for CSR 4.0 will include “purpose” as a primary priority; innovation, engagement, and collaboration with all partners; identification, involvement, and co-creation with all stakeholders; shared and integrated value at a deeper level; deep transformation and network creation in a new ecosystem; measurable Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with ongoing assessment and updating; systemic orientation at the leadership and employee levels; and cyclical social missions with environmental loops (Munro, 2020, pp. 217–219).

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GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

1. GENERATIONS AND STAGES OF CSR
2. THE TRIPLE CURSE OF MODERN CSR
3. PRINCIPLES OF CSR 2.0
4. CSR 1.0 VS CSR 2.0: MACRO AND MICRO LEVELS
5. THE DNA OF CSR 2.0
6. CSR 3.0 AND 4.0

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Topic 6. KEY EU DOCUMENTS AND POLICIES ON CSR/RBC

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KEY EU DOCUMENTS AND POLICIES ON CSR/RBC

1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union
2. Directives on CSR/RBC in Europe
3. Directive on Non-Financial Reporting
4. EU Directive on Corporate Sustainability Reporting
5. EU Sustainable Finance Strategy
6. Key Documents for CSR/RBC Policy

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1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union

The promotion of CSR as a distinct European strategy began one year after the adoption of the Millennium Development Goals and the establishment of the UN Convention, when the European Commission presented the Green Paper entitled *Promoting a European Framework for Corporate Social Responsibility* (2001). This initiative arose from new social expectations and concerns of the time, including the growing apprehension about the impact of economic activity on the environment (Commission of the European Communities, 2001). Notably, the Green Paper introduced the European approach to CSR, aiming to reflect and integrate it into the broader context of international initiatives such as the UNGC (Commission of the European Communities, 2001). This was the first step toward the European CSR strategy adopted in 2002, after which the European Commission launched a series of campaigns to promote the European approach to CSR, based on the understanding that CSR is “the responsibility of enterprises for their impacts on society” and describes what a company should do to meet this responsibility (European Commission, 2011, p. 2).

COMMISSION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITIES

GREEN PAPER

Promoting a European framework for Corporate Social Responsibility

(presented by the Commission)

European Commission. (2011). Corporate social responsibility: a new definition, a new agenda for action.
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_11_730

Green Paper called Promoting a European framework for Corporate Social Responsibility (2001)

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/document/print/en/doc_01_9/DOC_01_9_EN.pdf

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1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union

The actions of companies have a significant impact on the lives of citizens in the EU and around the world - not only in terms of the products and services they offer, or the jobs and opportunities they create, but also in terms of working conditions, human rights, health, the environment, innovation, education, and training.

For this reason, EU citizens rightfully expect companies to understand their positive and negative impacts on society and the environment, and therefore to prevent, manage, and mitigate any negative effects they may cause, including across global supply chains. The fulfilment of this duty is widely referred to as **Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)** or **Responsible Business Conduct (RBC)**.

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1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union

The Commission has defined CSR as the responsibility of enterprises for their impact on society, and therefore it should be managed by companies. Companies can become socially responsible by:

- Integrating social, environmental, ethical, consumer, and human rights concerns into their business strategy, and
- Conducting their activities in compliance with the law.

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1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union

Why is CSR important?

- **FOR BUSINESSES** - CSR and RBC provide important benefits in terms of risk management, cost savings, access to capital, customer relations, personnel management, operational stability, innovation capacity, and ultimately, profitability.
- **FOR THE EU ECONOMY** - CSR and RBC make companies more resilient and innovative, contributing to a more sustainable economy.
- **FOR SOCIETY** - CSR and RBC offer a set of values on which we can build a more cohesive society and base the transition to a sustainable economic system.

COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A renewed EU strategy 2011-14 for Corporate Social Responsibility /* COM/2011/0681 final */ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0681>

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1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union

Responsible Business Conduct (RBC)

This is an alternative term introduced by the OECD in close cooperation with business, trade unions, and non-governmental organizations.

The OECD defines RBC as ***“a positive contribution to economic, environmental, and social progress with a view to achieving sustainable development and avoiding and addressing adverse impacts associated with the enterprise’s direct and indirect operations, products, or services.”***

Responsible Business Conduct and the SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS <https://mneguidelines.oecd.org/RBC-and-the-sustainable-development-goals.pdf>

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1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union

Business and Human Rights

Human rights are becoming an increasingly important aspect of CSR/RBC, especially concerning companies' global supply chains. The UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights define what companies and governments should do to ensure that business does not have a negative impact on human rights. These principles were endorsed by the UN Human Rights Council in 2011, stating that businesses are specialized organs of society that are required to comply with all applicable laws and respect human rights. The EU endorsed the UN Guiding Principles in its 2015 Action Plan on Human Rights and Democracy and committed to supporting their implementation. Therefore, the European Commission has published a number of guidance materials and contributed to the development of National Action Plans (NAPs).

COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A renewed EU strategy 2011-14 for Corporate Social Responsibility /* COM/2011/0681 final */ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0681>

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1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union

Corporate Social Responsibility and Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are the most common type of business in the EU.

They may not be aware of or use the terms “CSR” or “RBC,” but due to their close relationships with employees, the local community, and their business partners, they often naturally adopt a responsible approach to business. For most SMEs, the process of achieving social responsibility goals is likely to remain informal and intuitive. Nevertheless, the European Commission promotes CSR/RBC among SMEs by developing guides and manuals on CSR.

COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A renewed EU strategy 2011-14 for Corporate Social Responsibility /* COM/2011/0681 final */ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0681>

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2. Directives on CSR/RBC in Europe

The two resolutions adopted on 6 February 2013 by the European Parliament prove that the project is in line with European policy on this issue. The first (#2012/2098(INI)) called “*Social responsibility of companies: responsible and transparent business behavior and sustainable growth*” <https://bit.ly/3u25rDU> that underlines transparency and champions the adoption of a proposal legislation permitting companies flexibility in acting and an adequate degree of compatibility as concerns the publication of extra-financial information to meet the demand of investors and other stakeholders. The resolution 2012/2098(INI) calls for “increased, more inclusive and more transparent monitoring of CSR principles in EU trade policy” <https://bit.ly/3u25rDU> and encourages the EU as well as the Member States “**to provide** concrete information on and **education and training in CSR**, so that enterprises can take full advantage of CSR and implement it in their organisational culture” <https://bit.ly/3u25rDU>. Moreover, in this resolution European Parliament points to “**the importance of involving small and medium-sized enterprises in CSR** and recognising their achievements in this area” <https://bit.ly/3u25rDU>.

The second European Parliament resolution (#2012/2097(INI)) is the “*Social responsibility of business: promoting the interests of society and a path to sustainable and inclusive recovery*” <https://bit.ly/3wYSHji> focuses on four priority areas: sustainable economic recovery, the implementation of CSR globally, the need for a multilateral approach and integration between the public and private sectors. Resolution 2012/2097(INI) brings to the notice “the **strategic role SMEs can play in fostering the uptake of CSR**, owing to their close links with the areas in which they operate”, stresses that “**CSR must also extend to enterprises’** behaviour towards and in **third countries**”, encourages “to **help businesses ... to become involved in CSR**”, **denounces** based on the continuing high levels of business engagement with **CSR it being a ‘luxury good’** supported by business only in times of prosperity, urges “to promote CSR ... in young entrepreneurship schemes” <https://bit.ly/3wYSHji>.

The European Commission emphasizes that “it is important to promote the application of high sustainability standards also in third countries.” Reflection Paper: Towards a Sustainable Europe by 2030.

<https://bit.ly/3uM4rVh>
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<https://bit.ly/3u25rDU>

<https://bit.ly/3wYSHji>

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2. Directives on CSR/RBC in Europe

European Parliament resolution of 6 February 2013 on corporate social responsibility: accountable, transparent and responsible business behaviour and sustainable growth (2012/2098(INI))
(2016/C 024/06)

A modern understanding of CSR: preliminary remarks

1. Stresses that business cannot take over public authorities' responsibility for promoting, implementing and monitoring social and environmental standards;
2. Emphasises that the current global economic crisis arose from fundamental errors with respect to transparency, accountability, responsibility and from short-termism, and that the EU has a duty to ensure that these lessons are learnt by all;
3. Takes the view that business can contribute to the development of a social market economy and to meeting the objectives of the Europe 2020 strategy, providing jobs and paving the way for economic recovery;
4. Believes that the debate on CSR should be placed in a broader setting which, while ensuring that CSR remains primarily a voluntary policy, also leaves room for dialogue on regulatory measures, wherever appropriate;
5. Endorses the new definition of CSR put forward by the Commission, which does away with the dichotomy between voluntary and compulsory approaches;
6. Considers corporate governance to be a key element of corporate social responsibility, especially as regards relations with public authorities and workers and their representative organisations and as regards policy on bonuses, compensation and salaries; believes that in particular in cases where a business is in difficulty, excessive bonuses, compensation and salaries paid to managers are incompatible with socially responsible behaviour;
7. Believes that a business's tax policy should be considered part and parcel of CSR and that socially responsible behaviour consequently leaves no room for strategies aimed at evading tax or exploiting tax havens;
8. Believes that when assessing the social responsibility of a company, it is necessary to take into account the behaviour of companies operating within its supply chain and, where applicable, of its subcontractors;

<https://bit.ly/3u25rDU>

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2. Directives on CSR/RBC in Europe

<https://bit.ly/3u25rDU>

European Parliament resolution of 6 February 2013 on corporate social responsibility: accountable, transparent and responsible business behaviour and sustainable growth (2012/2098(INI)) (2016/C 024/06)

CSR and SMEs: putting theory into practice

39. Draws attention to the special features of SMEs, which mainly operate at local and regional level inside specific sectors; considers it essential, therefore, for Union CSR policies, including national CSR action plans, to take proper account of the specific requirements of SMEs, to be in keeping with the 'think small first' principle, and to recognise the informal, intuitive SME approach to CSR;
40. Points to the importance of involving small and medium-sized enterprises in CSR and recognising their achievements in this area;
41. Acknowledges that many SMEs in Europe already undertake CSR policies, such as local employment, community engagement, applying good governance policies with their supply chain, etc; points out, however, that most of these SMEs do not know that they are actually implementing sustainability, CSR and good corporate governance practices; calls on the Commission, therefore, to first examine SMEs' current practices before considering specific CSR strategies for SMEs;
42. Voices its opposition to all measures that could result in additional administrative or financial constraints for SMEs, and its support for measures enabling SMEs to take joint action;
43. Calls on the Member States and regional authorities to make smart use of cohesion funding with a view to supporting CSR promotional activities carried out by SME intermediary organisations;
44. Calls on the Commission, in collaboration with Member States, SME intermediary organisations and other stakeholders, to devise strategies and measures to help SMEs pool best CSR practice, for instance by means of a database for collection of information on CSR policies implemented by SMEs, with details of projects carried out in the various Member States;
45. Recommends that CSR guides and handbooks should be drawn up for SMEs; stresses, in this connection, the urgent need for more academic research into ways of boosting acceptance of CSR among SMEs, as also into the economic, social and environmental impact of CSR policies at local and regional level;
46. Takes the view that, in order to have a real impact on poverty reduction, the CSR agenda should also focus on SMEs, since their cumulative social and environmental impact is significant;
47. Calls on the Commission and the Member States to devise development and support strategies aimed at disseminating CSR among SMEs;

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2. Directives on CSR/RBC in Europe

- Acting to **respect and protect human rights, providing adequate access to remedy** for victims of business-related abuses, whenever those rights are infringed;
- Encouraging companies to carry out **appropriate due diligence**, including with respect to human rights protection along their supply chains;
- Increasing transparency and promoting **sustainable finance**, including providing greater information on non-financial conduct of companies to citizens and investors;
- Encouraging **socially and environmentally-friendly business practices**, including through **public procurement**¹⁴;
- Promoting the implementation of CSR/RBC including UNGPs on Business and Human Rights **outside the EU** through EU trade and development policies and programmes, engagement in multilateral fora, as well as through bilateral cooperation with third countries;
- Developing dedicated approaches for **specific sectors** or company types;
- Pursuing **horizontal approaches**, including working with Member States on **National Action Plans**.

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3. Non-Financial Reporting Directive

The Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFR Directive) came into force in all EU Member States in 2018. Since then, all 28 countries have adapted the Directive into their national legislation, and companies are now required to comply with it.

The EU Non-Financial Reporting Directive is enshrined in the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU, allowing Member States to exceed the requirements set by the EU in matters of environmental protection.

The number of regulatory initiatives requiring the disclosure of non-financial information is growing rapidly. From 2013 to 2018, the number of registered regulations related to non-financial matters increased by 72%, and this trend is likely to continue.

At the same time, the cost of non-financial risk is rising. Between 2008 and 2012, the world's ten largest banks lost about USD 200 billion due to lawsuits for compensation and operational disruptions. Countries have adapted the NFR Directive to varying degrees — businesses must understand what each relevant country requires to effectively reduce risk.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014L0095>

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014L0095>

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3. Non-Financial Reporting Directive

To test the main hypotheses, the authors select 905 treated firms from the EU 28 + 2 countries for a difference-in-differences regression analysis of dependent variables from the Refinitiv ESG database

“The results suggest that the Directive influences sustainability reporting quantity and quality. Treated firms provide around 4 percentage points more sustainability information (i.e. availability) than propensity score matched control firms and are 19 percent more likely to receive external assurance (i.e. credibility). However, we also find that the Directive is not the decisive factor in the adoption of GRI guidelines (i.e. comparability)”.

Ottenstein, P., Erben, S., Jost, S., Weuster, C. W., & Zülch, H. (2022). From voluntarism to regulation: effects of Directive 2014/95/EU on sustainability reporting in the EU. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 23(1), 55–98. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAAR-03-2021-0075>

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

The EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) will amend the existing Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD). By expanding the scope of sustainability issues, the CSRD requires all large EU companies to implement mandatory sustainability reporting standards.

Companies must submit a report in compliance with the CSRD on January 1, 2024, for the 2023 financial year. For reporting companies, this will be a challenging task, as data collection and auditing are complex processes that require time and resources.

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Year	Categories of Companies Required to Start Reporting
2024	Companies already subject to NFRD (public companies with ≥ 500 employees)
2025	Large companies that have not previously reported (from 250 employees, etc.)
2026	Public small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)
2028	Foreign companies with branches or subsidiaries in the EU

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Criterion	Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD)	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)
Effective Date	2014 (applied since 2017)	Entered into force in January 2023, gradual implementation from 2024
Purpose	Require large companies to report on non-financial risks	Expand sustainability reporting requirements and improve quality, comparability, and verification
Covered Companies	Large public-interest companies with over 500 employees	Almost all large companies (from 250 employees) and all listed companies – including foreign companies
Obligation	Only for large public-interest entities	Significantly broader mandatory scope: medium, small public, and especially – foreign companies
Reporting Topics	Environment, social issues, human rights, anti-corruption	ESG (environment, social issues, governance), strategy, risks, impacts, double materiality
Reporting Format	No standardized format	ESRS (European Sustainability Reporting Standards)
Verification (Audit)	Not required	Mandatory limited assurance
Goal	Increase transparency in the non-financial field	Integrate sustainability into the financial system and increase investor trust
Link to Other Legislation	Partially linked to the Company Reporting Directive	Closely linked to the European Green Deal, SFDR, EU taxonomy
Double Materiality	Not mandatory	Mandatory – companies must report both on how their activities affect business and on risks and impacts

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Parameter	Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD)	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)
Main Company Category	Only large companies that are public-interest entities	All large companies, regardless of public status
Coverage Criteria	Companies with over 500 employees, listed on the stock exchange, banks, insurance companies	Companies meeting at least 2 out of 3 criteria: • >250 employees • >€40M turnover • >€20M balance sheet total
Medium-Sized Companies	✗ Not covered	✓ Covered if they meet the criteria
Small Companies (SMEs)	✗ Not covered	✓ Small public companies covered from 2026 (with simplified reporting)
Branches/Subsidiaries of Foreign Companies	✗ Not covered	✓ If they have over €150M turnover in the EU and at least 1 branch or subsidiary – required to report
Date of Implementation	2017	Starting from 2024 (gradually)

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Statistics on Company Coverage: NFRD vs CSRD

Criterion	NFRD	CSRD
Estimated number of covered companies in the EU	~11,700 companies	~50,000 companies
Number of covered companies in Ukraine (by analogy)	approximately ~100–200	potentially up to ~1,000+ (depending on implementation)
Coverage of large companies	✓ Only public companies with more than 500 employees	✓ All large companies (from 250 employees)
Medium-sized companies	✗ Not covered	✓ Covered if meeting two of the three criteria
Small companies (public)	✗ Not covered	✓ From 2026 — mandatory simplified reporting
Non-public companies	✗ Not covered	✓ If they are large or part of a group
Foreign companies operating in the EU	✗ Not covered	✓ From 2028, if EU turnover > €150 million

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Comparison of Reporting Content: NFRD vs CSRD

Criteria / Topics	NFRD	CSRD
General focus	Non-financial aspects of corporate activities	Full integration of sustainability and ESG into business strategy
Main topics	• Environment• Social issues• Human rights• Anti-corruption	• ESG: Environment, Social issues, Governance• Strategy• Business model• Sustainability goals
Risk management	Mentioned briefly	✓ Mandatory disclosure of risks, including sustainability risks
Double materiality	✗ Not mandatory	✓ Mandatory – must consider both business impact on the environment and ESG factors' impact on the business
Link to company strategy	Partially	✓ Must clearly demonstrate how ESG is integrated into strategy
Impact assessment	Not detailed	✓ Mandatory disclosure of significant company impacts on people, environment, and economy
Indicators and metrics	Free format, no clear standards	✓ Must use unified ESRS standards
Digital structure (XBRL)	✗ Not required	✓ Required digital tagging for data submission

4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Double Materiality

Criteria	Explanation	In NFRD	In CSRD
What is double materiality?	A concept that requires reporting from two perspectives: 1. Financial materiality – how ESG factors (risks, climate change, etc.) affect the company’s financial indicators. 2. Impact materiality – how the company’s activities impact the environment, society, and human rights. Ensures a comprehensive understanding of the connection between business and sustainability.	✗ Not explicitly mentioned	✓ Mandatory and clearly defined
Purpose		May be partially mentioned Mentioned only indirectly Limited	✓ Must be disclosed in detail ✓ Full disclosure of impacts and interactions ✓ Strategic foundation of reporting
Example 1: Climate change	• Financial: how climate change may affect asset value • Impact: company’s CO ₂ emissions	✗ Only risks or impacts	✓ Both aspects mandatory
Example 2: Employee rights	• Financial: strikes may threaten profits • Impact: working conditions, gender pay gap	Partial disclosure	✓ Must cover both risks and impacts
Importance for stakeholders	Allows for considering both investor interests and the company’s impact on society	Limited	✓ All stakeholders considered
Application in reporting practice	Forms the basis for comprehensive ESG reporting	Recommended	✓ Mandatory according to CSRD

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Reporting format: NFRD vs CSRD

Criteria	NFRD	CSRD
Presence of a single standard	✗ None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ ESRS (European Sustainability Reporting Standards) introduced
Submission format	In any format, often as a separate section of the annual report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Mandatory structured format, integrated into or alongside financial reporting
Comparability	Limited – depends on the company’s approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Significantly improved through unification of formats and requirements
Digital submission (XBRL)	✗ Not provided for	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Mandatory – use of electronic format for publication and analysis
Preparation based on standards	Could refer to GRI, IIRC, etc. (but not mandatory)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Use of European ESRS standards is mandatory

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4. THE CORPORATE SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING DIRECTIVE (CSRD)

Assurance: NFRD vs CSRD

Criteria	NFRD	CSRD
Audit requirement	✗ Not required	✓ Mandatory audit (at the level of limited assurance)
Type of audit	None	Minimum level: limited assurance
Auditing organization	—	Auditor or independent certified body
Purpose of the audit	—	Verification of the accuracy and completeness of disclosed data
Possible increase in requirements	—	In the future, a shift to reasonable assurance (higher level) is expected

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5. EU SUSTAINABLE FINANCE STRATEGY

EU SUSTAINABLE FINANCE STRATEGY

One of the goals of the European Green Deal is to mobilise private investment to transition to a climate-neutral economy.

The EU aims to become the first climate-neutral continent, and the European Green Deal serves as the roadmap to achieve this goal.

Corporate disclosure of climate-related information

Guidance for companies on how to report on the impacts of their business on the climate and on the impacts of climate change on their business.

Disclosures

Guidance for companies on how to report on the impacts of their business on the climate and on the impacts of climate change on their business.

EU labels for benchmarks (climate, ESG) and benchmarks' ESG disclosures

Make benchmark methodologies more transparent when it comes to ESG & put forward standards for the methodology of low-carbon and ESG benchmarks in EU.

EU taxonomy for sustainable activities

What the EU is doing to create an EU-wide classification system for sustainable activities.

European green bond standard

How an EU-wide standard could encourage market participants to issue & invest in EU green bonds and improve the effectiveness & credibility of the market.

International Platform on Sustainable Finance

Forum for dialogue between policymakers, with the aim of increasing the amount of private capital being invested in environmentally sustainable investments

Overview of sustainable finance

A Commission workstream that supports the European green deal aim of channelling private investment towards the transition to a climate-neutral economy.

Sustainability-related disclosure in the financial services sector

What the obligations are for manufacturers of financial products and financial advisers towards end-investors.

Tools and standards

Tools and standards

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6. KEY EU DOCUMENTS AND POLICIES ON CSR/RBC

KEY EU DOCUMENTS AND POLICIES ON CSR/RBC

Назва	Покликання
A renewed EU strategy 2011-14 for corporate social responsibility	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0681
Action plan on human rights and democracy (2015-2019)	https://ec.europa.eu/anti-trafficking/eu-policy/action-plan-human-rights-and-democracy-2015-2019_en
Communication on the next steps for a sustainable European Future	https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sites/devco/files/communication-next-steps-sustainable-europe-20161122_en.pdf
Reflection paper: towards a sustainable Europe by 2030	https://ec.europa.eu/commission/publications/reflection-paper-towards-sustainable-europe-2030_en
Directive 2014/95/EU on non-financial reporting	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014L0095
United Nations global compact	http://www.unglobalcompact.org/
United Nations guiding principles on business and human Rights	http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/GuidingPrinciplesBusinessHR_EN.pdf
UN 2030 agenda for sustainable development	https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/development-agenda/
ISO 26000 guidance standard on social responsibility	https://www.iso.org/iso-26000-social-responsibility.html
OECD guidelines for multinational enterprises	http://www.oecd.org/corporate/mne/
OECD due diligence guidance for responsible business conduct	http://mneguidelines.oecd.org/OECD-Due-Diligence-Guidance-for-Responsible-Business-Conduct.pdf
Social policy principles for multinational enterprises by the International Labour Organization	http://www.ilo.org/empent/Publications/WCMS_094386/lang--en/index.htm

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KEY EU DOCUMENTS AND POLICIES ON CSR/RBC

1. Emergence of CSR/RBC in the European Union
2. Directives on CSR/RBC in Europe
3. Directive on Non-Financial Reporting
4. EU Directive on Corporate Sustainability Reporting
5. EU Sustainable Finance Strategy
6. Key Documents for CSR/RBC Policy

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Embracing EU corporate social
responsibility: challenges and
opportunities of business-society bonds
transformation in Ukraine

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Topic 7. CSR/RBC CASES OF LEADING COMPANIES

Oleh PASKO

<https://eecore.snau.edu.ua/komanda-proiektu/oleg-pasko/>

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CSR/RBC CASES OF LEADING COMPANIES

1. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY:
CASES OF 5 INTERNATIONAL
COMPANIES IN UKRAINE
2. CSR/RBC: SUCCESSFUL CASES OF
GLOBAL COMPANIES

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1. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: CASES OF 5 INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES IN UKRAINE

Unilever committed to producing 100% recyclable and reusable plastic packaging by 2025, while also reducing the use of virgin plastic by 50%.

Between 2014–2019, under the Domestos brand, the company carried out a campaign *“In a clean world, children don’t get sick”*. The three top-ranked schools in the program received restroom renovations in line with international standards.

At the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic (March–April 2020), Unilever donated over 5,000 liters of Domestos to 50 hospitals across 24 regions of Ukraine. That same year, Domestos supplied disinfectants to 1,700 schools to ensure safe external testing (ZNO). In 2020, the brand also launched a joint project with UNICEF *“Back to School”*, which included training programs for staff, children, and parents on surface hygiene to prepare schools for reopening.

In 2019, Unilever initiated an eco flash mob in which employees simultaneously planted 8,000 saplings.

Additionally, in late March 2021, the Dove brand launched the *#ShowUs* project in Ukraine. The campaign called on media and advertisers to reject stereotypes, embrace the diversity of women’s beauty, and use a photo bank with unretouched images of real Ukrainian women.

<https://bit.ly/3JLcS71>

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1. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: CASES OF 5 INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES IN UKRAINE

L'ORÉAL®

As part of its sustainable development program “*L'Oréal for the Future*”, all company sites will become carbon-neutral by 2025. Moreover, 100% of plastic packaging will be reusable or recyclable.

The company has committed €100 million in impact investments to ecosystem restoration and the development of a circular economy.

The general education program “*Beauty for All*” offers free hairdressing training for women who have suffered from domestic or gender-based violence. Over four years, 100 women graduated from the program, and in 2021, another 64 completed the training in Kyiv and Lviv.

On March 8, 2020, L'Oréal Paris launched the *Stand Up* initiative to prevent harassment in public places. More than 400,000 people worldwide have completed the training. On March 8, 2021, the campaign was also launched in Ukraine.

The company invested €50 million in a foundation supporting vulnerable categories of women.

The Ukrainian *L'Oréal-UNESCO “For Women in Science” Award* supports women in science and encourages them to pursue scientific careers. In 2021, more than 170 female scientists participated, including 115 candidates of sciences and 52 doctors of sciences.

<https://bit.ly/3JLcS71>

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1. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: CASES OF 5 INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES IN UKRAINE

In mid-September, the company introduced its global strategy *PepsiCo Positive*:

- Achieve carbon neutrality by 2040.
- Replenish 100% of the water used by the company by 2030.
- Implement regenerative agriculture practices on more than 3 million hectares of farmland used by PepsiCo's suppliers.
- Source agricultural raw materials exclusively from responsible suppliers.
- Reduce plastic in beverage packaging by 50% by 2030.

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1. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: CASES OF 5 INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES IN UKRAINE

Deloitte.

The main focus is on driving positive social change through volunteer activities and financial support of projects. Deloitte's strategic goal is to impact the lives of 100 million people worldwide through education by 2030.

Through the **Deloitte WorldClass Lectures** project, organized jointly with Pro Bono Club Ukraine, company employees share expertise with the nonprofit sector. Topics include leadership, digital literacy, project management, branding, creative solutions, and team management. Since spring 2020, Deloitte has held 13 webinars with nearly 500 participants. Employees also share their skills, knowledge, and time on a volunteer basis. In 2021, Deloitte staff “invested” 2,150 hours in educational, charitable, and pro bono volunteer projects.

Deloitte is also a partner of the **Global Teacher Prize**, ensuring compliance with the rules during the selection and recognition of winners.

Another educational initiative is **Work & Study** — a dual learning program in finance. In the pilot project with Kyiv National Economic University, 11 first-year students combined study with work experience at Deloitte's office.

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1. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: CASES OF 5 INTERNATIONAL COMPANIES IN UKRAINE

infopulse

Key focus in 2021 — quality IT education, healthcare, and combating climate change.

- In the field of education, Infopulse specialists acted as coordinators and mentors for a group of students and professors from the National Technical University of Ukraine. Together, they developed websites for the Kyiv children's choir "Shchedryk" and the educational platform "Inclusive Hub."
- In summer 2021, Infopulse experts provided free training to 200 people within the Microsoft Power Apps Developer Program. After completing the program, seven participants undertook internships at Infopulse, and four joined the company's team.
- The "**Health Truck**" project supported hospitals by supplying protective equipment and materials to 26 medical institutions across Ukraine. The company allocated UAH 1,004,106 for this initiative.
- Infopulse also assisted the "**Crab**" **Childhood Cancer Foundation** (part of Childhood Cancer International) by purchasing three volumetric infusion pumps used in chemotherapy.
- The company organizes corporate social teambuilding events, including waste collection and tree planting. In summer 2021, dozens of volunteers cleaned up Obolon embankment and Holosiivskyi Park in Kyiv. On the company's 30th anniversary, Infopulse planted 30 trees in Nivky Park (Kyiv) and contributed to planting 285 additional trees. In Lviv, the company planted 6,500 seedlings (oak, maple, and fir) in the Lelekhovske forestry.

<https://bit.ly/3JLcS71>

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2. Innovations in renewable energy sources: Johnson & Johnson

Our Renewable Electricity Footprint

An excellent example of CSR at the forefront is the large pharmaceutical corporation **Johnson & Johnson**.

For three decades, the company has been focusing on reducing its environmental impact. Their initiatives range from using wind power to providing safe water to communities around the world. By acquiring a private energy supplier in the Texas Panhandle, the company reduced pollution while offering a renewable, cost-effective alternative to electricity.

Johnson & Johnson continues to explore renewable energy options with the goal of covering **100% of its energy needs from renewable sources by 2025**.

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2. Social issues: Google

Google is trusted not only for its green initiatives, but also because of its outspoken CEO Sundar Pichai. He has spoken out against social issues, including former President Donald Trump's anti-Muslim comments.

Google also received the highest CSR score in 2018 from the Reputation Institute, in part because their data centers use 50% less energy than others in the world.

They have also committed over \$1 billion to renewable energy projects and enable other businesses to reduce their environmental impact through services like Gmail..

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2. Sustainability: Coca-Cola

As a brand, Coca-Cola has a strong focus on sustainability.

Key areas include climate, packaging and agriculture, as well as water and product quality.

Their message is “a world without waste”, with the aim of collecting and recycling every bottle, making packaging 100% recyclable and replacing all the water used to produce drinks back into the environment to ensure water safety.

They aim to reduce their carbon footprint by 25% by 2030. In 2021, Coca-Cola introduced its first-ever beverage bottle made from 100% plant-based plastic.

“Our goal is to develop sustainable solutions for the entire industry. We want other companies to join us and move forward together. “We don't view renewable or recycled content as areas where we want to gain a competitive advantage,” said Dana Breed, global director of research and development, packaging and sustainability at The Coca-Cola Company.

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2. CARBON NEUTRALITY and fair payment: Ford Motor Company

Ford has big plans for CSR. Their mission is to “build a better world where everyone is free to move and pursue their dreams. They have increased their investment in electrification to \$22 billion (up from \$11 billion) and aim to have their vehicles carbon neutral by 2050.” “We are committed to carbon neutrality,” said Bob Holycross, Ford’s vice president and chief sustainability officer, environment and safety. “It’s the right thing to do for our customers, the planet and Ford. Ninety-five percent of our carbon emissions today come from our vehicles, operations and suppliers, and we are addressing all three areas with urgency and optimism. Interestingly, the company is also focusing on pay equity. They are conducting a diversity, equity, and inclusion audit, while also implementing a global pay ratio (including gender) to create a level playing field for all employees.

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2. Workers' rights: Netflix i Spotify

On the social front, companies like Netflix and Spotify offer benefits to support their employees and families.

Netflix offers 52 weeks of paid parental leave for parents (including foster children). This can be taken at any time, whether it's the child's first year or another time that suits their needs. By comparison, the average is 18 weeks at other major tech companies.

Spotify offers a similar program, but with a shorter duration of 24 weeks of paid leave. The company believes that the launch of this initiative has led to a surge in external job applications that has never diminished.

When it comes to social causes, Netflix and Spotify use their social media platforms to show support for movements like Pride Month, environmental sustainability, and Black Lives Matter. Netflix is an example of how to target and reach niche and minority audiences through smart social media.

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2. Access to medical care: Pfizer

When disaster strikes, emergency healthcare is critical. To help in these circumstances, Pfizer has a three-pronged approach: product donations, grants, and access solutions. Grants have been provided to countries like Haiti in the aftermath of Hurricane Matthew and the global refugee crisis in Europe and the Middle East. This money is provided in partnership with community organizations to reach as many people as possible. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Pfizer provided \$5 million through its Global Health Grants Program to improve recognition, diagnosis, treatment, and patient management. In addition, grants have been provided to clinics, medical centers, and hospitals to improve care and outcomes for patients with COVID-19.

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2. Charitable donations: Wells Fargo

Each year, Wells Fargo donates up to 1.5% of its revenue to charitable causes through philanthropy to more than 14,500 nonprofits, such as food banks and incubators (plant science and renewable energy), to accelerate the time-to-market of startups.

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the company has donated \$6.25 million to support domestic and global efforts.

This includes \$1 million to the CDC Foundation, \$250,000 to the International Medical Corps in 30 countries, and \$5 million to local efforts to address community needs.

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2. Mass campaigns: TOMS

TOMS' mission is to donate a pair of shoes for every pair sold, and this has resulted in the donation of over 100 million pairs of shoes to children in need. These profits have been used to help people with vision impairments by providing prescription glasses and treatment, providing "safe" drinking water, and creating businesses in developing countries to create jobs.

As the company has come under fire from NGOs for creating a dependency on free shoes and the collapse of the local shoe industry, TOMS has reevaluated its strategy. Instead of focusing on free shoes, the company now **DONATES ONE THIRD OF ITS PROFITS** to grassroots campaigns. This includes the COVID-19 Relief Fund and racial justice campaigns like Black Lives Matter.

"We've learned that providing shoes, vision, and safe water for over a decade has been a great start — the right start — to creating meaningful change. But the decision to award impact grants will allow our community to do even more. Instead of giving away shoes, we're giving away $\frac{1}{3}$ of our profits. In other words, \$1 for every \$3 we make, which is about as much as a company can give away, keeping the spiritual light alive." –TOMS Impact Report 2019-2020.

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2. Climate neutral: Bosch

Bosch has set itself ambitious environmental goals to reduce its environmental footprint through climate action, water use and the circular economy.

This ambition appears to have paid off and paved the way for other global companies, as 400 of its subsidiaries are now climate neutral.

The company now wants to reduce upstream (purchased goods and services) and downstream (product use) emissions by 15% by 2030. "Having achieved our initial targets for Scope 1 and 2, we are now addressing Scope 3 emissions with the same degree of rigor, setting specific targets and milestones for the coming years." - Thorsten Kallweit, Head of Health and Sustainability

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2. Clean technology: GE

It's been more than a decade since General Electric launched Ecomagination, its renewable energy business strategy with a mission to double the use of clean technologies and generate \$20 billion in revenue from green products.

As part of the Ecomagination Challenge launched last year, GE awarded five people \$100,000 each for developing innovations such as an inflatable wind turbine, a smart water meter, a cyber-secured grid infrastructure, and short-circuit and shutdown technology.

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2. Workplace diversity and inclusion: Starbucks

Starbucks wanted to diversify its workforce and provide opportunities for certain cohorts. The company pledged to hire 25,000 U.S. military veterans and their spouses by 2025 as part of its corporate social responsibility efforts.

The company hit that milestone six years early and now hires 5,000 veterans and military members each year.

To address racial and social equity, Starbucks announced a mentorship program to connect black, indigenous, and people of color (BIPOC) with senior leadership and invest in partnerships. The chain also aims to have 30% BIPOC representation in corporate roles and 40% in retail and manufacturing by 2025.

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2. Ecological development: New Belgium Brewing Company

This brewery, which is entirely owned by its employees through a stock ownership plan, is focused on sustainability.

Its Fort Collins, Colorado, brewery generates electricity using solar panels and wastewater, and aims to make all of its beer carbon neutral by 2030.

The company also donates \$1 from every barrel sold to support its charitable initiatives, values, and goals.

“We believe that social and environmental well-being are intricately intertwined,” says Katie Wallace, director of CSR.

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2. Local communities: The Walt Disney Company

Disney committed to reducing its carbon footprint in its 2020 CSR report, with goals for zero net greenhouse gas emissions, zero waste, and a commitment to water conservation.

They actively enforce strict international labor policies to protect the safety and rights of their employees.

They are also active in the community and encourage their employees to do the same. When their parks closed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, Disney focused their CSR efforts on local communities. They provided \$27 million in food and PPE donations from closed parks and production facilities, and encouraged employees to participate in virtual volunteering.

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2. Packaging: LEGO

Lego is investing \$400 million over the next three years to accelerate its sustainability efforts. Their ultimate goal as a modern superbrand is to GO WITHOUT SINGLE-SPECIAL PLASTIC PACKAGING FOR THEIR PRODUCTS BY 2025, SO THAT ALL PACKAGING IS ECOLOGICAL. From 2021, they will trial paper bags in boxes in partnership with the Forest Stewardship Council.

They are also investing in more sustainable products that create zero waste and are carbon neutral. LEGO Group CEO Niels B. Christiansen said: “We cannot lose sight of the fundamental challenges that future generations will face. It is crucial that we take urgent action now to take care of the planet and future generations. As a company that looks to children as role models, we are inspired by the millions of children calling for more urgent action on climate change.”

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2. Social media and journalism: The Washington Post

In the wake of fake news, news outlets are turning to social media platforms like TikTok to reach new audiences and combat misinformation about issues like the U.S. election and the coronavirus.

The Washington Post is one example of a news brand successfully using TikTok. Their tagline is “We are the newspaper,” and their TikTok profile already has 1 million followers (and counting).

Their goal? To attract new readers and build trust through short videos and viral content.

According to Dave Jorgensen, the Post’s social media guru, TikTok’s rapid growth is because the platform has increased trust between the newspaper and its followers. He believes TikTok is journalism in every sense of the word. “Almost every other TikTok has some kind of news related to it, and we’re delivering the news to the users. That’s what journalism is all about — delivering the news in the way you can, responsibly.”

The Washington Post

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2. Philanthropic model 1-1-1 Salesforce

In addition to its leadership in the technology space, cloud software giant Salesforce is a pioneer in corporate philanthropy.

Since its inception, the company has championed its 1-1-1 philanthropic model, which involves donating one percent of its product, one percent of its equity, and one percent of its employee time to communities and nonprofits.

To date, Salesforce employees have volunteered more than 5 million hours. The company has also awarded more than \$406 million in grants and donated to more than 40,000 nonprofits and educational institutions. In addition, through partnerships with the San Francisco Unified School District and Oakland Unified School District, Salesforce has helped reduce algebra repetition rates and helped a high percentage of students earn A's or B's in computer science.

As the company's revenue continues to grow, Salesforce is a shining example of the idea that profit-making and social impact initiatives don't have to be at odds.

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2. Social mission Ben & Jerry

For Ben & Jerry's, making a positive impact on society is as important as making premium ice cream.

In 2012, the company became a Certified B Corporation, a business that combines purpose and profit while adhering to the highest standards of social and environmental performance, public transparency, and legal accountability.

As part of its overall commitment to leading with progressive values, the ice cream maker founded the Ben & Jerry's Foundation in 1985, an organization dedicated to supporting grassroots movements that drive social change. Each year, the foundation awards approximately \$2.5 million in grants to organizations in Vermont and the United States. Grant recipients include the United Labor Association, an advocacy group committed to ending poverty, and the Clean Air Coalition, an environmental and justice organization based in New York.

In 2014, the foundation received the National Committee for Responsive Philanthropy Award, and it continues to sponsor efforts to find solutions to systemic problems at both the local and national levels.

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2. Social impact Levi Strauss

In addition to being one of the most successful fashion brands in history, Levi's was also one of the first to push for a more ethical and sustainable supply chain.

In 1991, the brand created the Terms of Participation, which established a global code of conduct for the supply chain and set standards for worker rights, a safe work environment, and a sustainable manufacturing process. To maintain its commitment in a changing world, Levi's regularly updates its Terms of Participation.

In 2011, on the 20th anniversary of its Code of Conduct, Levi's announced its Worker Wellbeing initiative to implement further programs aimed at the health and well-being of supply chain workers. Since 2011, the Worker Wellbeing initiative has expanded to 12 countries and more than 100,000 employees have benefited. In 2016, the brand expanded the initiative, pledging to expand the program to more than 300,000 employees and to produce more than 80 percent of its products in Worker Wellbeing factories by 2025.

For its ongoing efforts to support the well-being of its people and the environment, Levi's was named one of the 2020 winners of Engage for Good's Golden Halo Award, the highest honor for socially responsible companies.

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CSR/RBC CASES OF LEADING COMPANIES

1. CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY:

CASES OF 5 INTERNATIONAL

COMPANIES IN UKRAINE

2. CSR/RBC: SUCCESSFUL CASES OF

GLOBAL COMPANIES